

ACA-401/ACA-401D COURSEPACK (PERIOD 1)

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PREFACE

In its sixth iteration, the period one course pack delivers essential guidance for both international academics and professionals on the fundamentals of paper writing. Designed for students at Euclid University, this comprehensive module serves as a foundational resource, covering key aspects such as essay composition, punctuation, plagiarism avoidance, and adherence to style conventions. Notably, it aids students in distinguishing between US and UK English usage, promoting consistency throughout their writing.

Moreover, this coursepack offers insight into the instructor's paper review process, showcasing exemplary responses to student submissions. It is essential for participants to possess moderate to advanced proficiency in Microsoft Word, as the course introduces the utilization of response paper templates and explores advanced features like the "Styles" menu and the "Review" tab.

Beyond its immediate scope, this coursepack primes students for subsequent periods by providing a preview of forthcoming topics and methodologies. It serves as a robust foundation for continued academic and professional growth, offering a glimpse into the strategies and expectations of future coursework.

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CONTENTS

PREFACE.....	3
CONTENTS.....	4
1) CHAPTER ONE: ESSAY WRITING.....	6
Academic Essay	7
Starting the Essay	7
Researching the Topic	8
Organizing your Ideas.....	9
Writing the Essay.....	10
Referencing the Essay.....	11
Editing the Essay	11
Handing the Essay In	12
Some Rules of Thumb for Writing a Paper	12
2) CHAPTER TWO: PUNCTUATIONS	15
3) CHAPTER THREE: AMERICAN VS. BRITISH ENGLISH.....	24
Introduction	25
Different Pronunciation, Although Same Spelling	25
Different Spelling, Although Same Pronunciation	25
Same Term, Different but Similar Spelling and Pronunciation.....	26
Same Words, But Different or Additional Meanings	26
Grammar, Syntax, Punctuation, General Usage	26
Differences in Usage with SBE 'Large Collective Nouns'	26
Differences in Usage with SBE 'Pluralised Adjectives'	27
Other Common Usage Differences.....	27
Same Concept, Different Terms or Expressions; (or) Same Word, Differences in Style, Connotation and Frequency.....	28
"Creativity": Spinoffs; Combos; Referencing of Current Events and Brands.....	28
Euphemistic References	29
"Equality" Vocabulary	29
"Politically Correct" References.....	29
'Ethnolects': "Black English" (specific terminology in cultural context).....	30
Yiddish and Ethnic Jewish Influence (lexical & structural) on SAE.....	30
Various Jargons; Changing Cultural References.....	30
Regional Variation, Identity, Stereotyping	30
i) Variation in Terminology.....	30
"Four-letter words," Obscenities and Implied Obscenities	31
Examples of Differences with Punctuation and Dates	31
Periods, Commas, and Quotation Marks	31
Punctuation with Business (Formal) vs. Social (Informal) Letters	32
4) CHAPTER FOUR: PLAGIARISM.....	33
What is Plagiarism?	34
When to Give Credit to Author?	34

Why Mention the Source?	34
So How do we Avoid Plagiarism?	34
How to Cite/What Does it Mean to Cite?	34
i) In-Text Citation	35
ii) What are Quotations?	35
iii) A Few Tips about Quotations	36
iv) Paraphrases	36
When NOT to Cite	37
Signal Phrases	38
List of Works Cited	38
Format to Follow	38
Achieving “Logical Flow”	39
5) CHAPTER FIVE: WHAT IS A STYLE GUIDE, AND WHY WOULD I NEED ONE? ...	40
6) CHAPTER SIX: CMS CRIB SHEET	43
Chicago Style and Usage	44
Abbreviations	44
Capitalization	45
Compound Words	46
Italics & Quotation Marks	47
Numbers	47
Quotations	48
Chicago Page Formats	50
Footnotes	52
Headings & Lists	52
Tables	53
Chicago Endnotes & Footnotes	54
Chicago Bibliographies	56
7) CHAPTER SEVEN: LATIN ABBREVIATIONS AND EXPRESSIONS	58
Common Latin Abbreviations Used in Writing	59
Commonly Used Latin Expressions	62
8) CHAPTER EIGHT: SAMPLE CORRECTIONS TO PAPERS	65
REFERENCES	72

1) CHAPTER ONE: ESSAY WRITING

Have a general overview on the basics of essay writing

Understand the steps for writing a good essay

Understand some rule of thumbs for writing a paper

Academic Essay

There are many types of essays, but we will discuss essays intended for academic purposes in this chapter. Academic essay or scholarly writing is nonfictional writing produced as part of academic work. Examples of academic writing include research findings or report on empirical fieldwork which may not or may be published in journals, books, newspapers, or other periodicals (or remain as manuscripts, theses, or dissertations); monograph; conference paper; book or literature review; explication; technical report; translation; students' presentations; as well as undergraduate versions on the above.

Nearly all academic writing shares some kind of formal prose register, citations and references to other works, use of stable rhetorical moves to define the project's scope, position it in relevant research, and advance new contributions.

Academic essays seek to provide answer(s) to hypotheses, aiming to communicate ideas based on evidence.

Starting the Essay

The steps for writing are not rigidly linear. However, of course, some basic steps are taken in writing an academic essay. The following steps are required to be undertaken before starting the essay.

- Early start-up: It is best to start as early as possible. One of the initial things required for writing is to have enough time to read, research the topic, think, and write. It is never advisable to procrastinate
- Defining the question and analyzing the task: While defining and writing everything one knows about a topic is important, analyzing and presenting the answers to the question is key
- Drafting an initial plan: Having a plan for going about the essay is very important. This should include your initial thoughts and ideas about the research topic, which should constitute your preliminary essay plan that will help guide your research. If an essay plan is written correctly, it will help you work out how you will answer the question and the type of information to use

Figure 1: Basic Steps in Writing an Essay

Researching the Topic

After understanding the topic, the next important thing is reading and researching what to write. Reading and researching will give the knowledge and evidence to develop a thesis and answer.

While reading on the topic, it is important that you answer the following question.

- ✓ What do I already know about the topic?
- ✓ What do I need to read and know to write the essay?
- ✓ Is this material useful to my topic/argument?
- ✓ Can I use this material to support my answer?

It is essential to make some notes while you read, as this will be the basis for your essay. However, in your initial reading photocopies, it is advised you underline or highlight relevant information, which you can return to when you re-read and take notes.

While reading, always keep the topic or question of the essay clearly in mind and note that you must use sound evidence to support your argument. Therefore, spend much time looking for relevant information (such as summaries, direct quotes from texts, useful examples, case studies, or statistics).

The notes should come from any information source, including copying the bibliographic details or everything you read. Include the author's name, date, title, publisher, place of publication, and other relevant details.

Reading lists:

If you are given a list of suggested readings, consult as many as possible. Otherwise, locate relevant material in the library. Use the catalogue to perform topic and subject searches. Once you have your readings:

- use the table of contents and the index to find relevant material
- skim through the text to locate specific information
- when you find something, you need to read closely, flag the pages with a post-it notes so you can return for a close reading
- photocopy useful sections of texts so you can underline and make notes.

Thinking it through:

Essay writing requires both creative and critical thinking.

- Creative thinking encourages you to broaden your ideas. Try techniques like brainstorming or mind mapping.
- Critical thinking encourages you to narrow the focus or scope of your ideas (for example, asking why an example is important to your argument).

Your essay should be balanced: that is, it should include a range of information and viewpoints from different authors that explore the key arguments and relevant aspects of a particular topic.

Do not only include evidence that agrees with what you are arguing; if there are different or opposing views, then they need to be examined.

You need to evaluate differing arguments - explain why one argument is more convincing than another and how they relate to the conclusion your essay arrives at.

Organizing your Ideas

After reading and researching, your ideas become more developed. It is time to write an essay plan which will help you work out how to answer the question and how the essay will be structured. Draw up a plan while factoring in the following:

- ✓ Decide on a possible answer to the question (in terms of the research you did)
- ✓ Select the information you will use to answer the question
- ✓ Look through your notes and choose examples to provide evidence to support your answer

- ✓ Decide which points you will discuss and in which order
- ✓ Write the above points in a sketch form as this will be your essay plan

Writing the Essay

The first step is to produce the first draft according to the structure and framework of the essay. The draft is like the raw material you refine through editing and redrafting. The details of the essay will become much simpler once you have a draft.

The structure of the essay should be in the following format.

Essay paragraphs

Each paragraph in the body of the essay should deal with one main point/ aspect of your answer.

Each paragraph should contain:

1. a topic sentence that states the main or controlling idea;
2. supporting sentences to explain and develop the point you are making;
3. evidence. Most of the time, your point should be supported by some form of evidence from your reading, or by an example drawn from the subject area.
4. analysis. Do not just leave the evidence hanging there - analyze and interpret it! Comment on the implication/ significance/impact.

Finish off the paragraph with a critical conclusion you have drawn from the evidence.

Tips for effective writing

Start writing early - the earlier, the better. Starting cuts down on anxiety beats procrastination and gives you time to develop your ideas.

Do not try to write an essay from beginning to end (especially not in a single study session).

Begin with what you are ready to write - a plan, a sentence. Start with the body and work paragraph by paragraph.

Write the introduction and conclusion after the body. Once you know what your essay is about, then write the introduction and conclusion.

Keep the essay' question in mind. Do not lose track of the question or task. Keep it in mind as you draft and edit and work out your argument.

Revise your first draft extensively. Make sure the entire essay flows and that the paragraphs are in a logical order.

Put the essay aside for a few days. This allows you to consider your essay with a fresh eye.

Proof-read your final draft carefully.

Check spelling and punctuation.

Referencing the Essay

It is important to note that all academic essays **MUST** contain references. Only references guard against plagiarism which is a serious academic offense.

It is necessary that you inquire and understand the referencing style of the faculty, school, or journal. Some will provide guidance on the referencing standard they prefer. However, other schools (such as EUCLID) will accept any form of referencing if it is strict in its format and consistent throughout the paper.

Editing the Essay

Essays get dramatically improved upon careful editing. An essay is often recommended to be kept aside for a few days before editing. This practice gives you time to think further about your answer and arguments and return to your essay with a fresh perspective. If you find that you need more information or there are deficiencies in your arguments, be focused and calm in fixing the problem.

Consider the following key points when editing the essay.

- Check the overall structure of your essay; does it have a clear introduction, body, and conclusion?
- Make sure that each paragraph has a clear main point that relates to the argument. Make sure that the paragraphs are arranged in a logical sequence.
- Revise sentences. Make sure the words you use mean what you think they mean. Check punctuation and spelling. A good dictionary is a useful tool.
- Check transition signals. Be sure that a reader can follow the sequence of ideas from sentence to sentence, and from paragraph to paragraph.

Questions to ask yourself

- Have I answered the question as directly and comprehensively as possible?
- Does the argument make sense? Is it balanced and well researched?
- Is the evidence relevant to and supportive of my argument?
- Have I used a consistent citation style? Have I referenced all my quotes and paraphrases?
- If there were any special instructions or guidelines for this assignment, have I followed them?
- Have I remained within the set word limit?

Handing the Essay In

The last step is to hand the essay in. It is essential to read the guidelines of the course and follow them. Find out how the lecturer/ tutor would like assignments presented and ensure you comply with the requirement.

In general, note the following when handing in the essay.

- Make sure you know the date the assignment is due. Submitting late work usually incurs a late penalty.
- Make sure you know where and to whom your assignment should be submitted.
- Most assignments require a cover sheet (available from your school office).
- Do not submit your essay in a plastic folder or sleeve (unless you are asked to do so).
- Ensure your essay is formatted correctly. Use double-line spacing and a readable font (size 12 at least). Number pages and set wide margins.
- Print on one side of the page only.
- Staple your essay in the top left-hand corner.
- Keep an extra copy for yourself.

Some Rules of Thumb for Writing a Paper

Here are some suggestions for writing papers. Please read through them before you write the first paper.

State the main thesis of your paper at (or near) the beginning: preferably in the opening paragraph. It is not bad to say something like: "I will argue that" If you do not have a thesis, get one.

Stay focused: Your papers should critically assess some important aspect of one of the theories we have been discussing: the thesis of your paper, stated near the beginning (see point 1 above), will say what that aspect is. Before getting to the evaluation, you will need to describe the relevant aspect(s) of the theory you are assessing. But do not try to provide a comprehensive overview of the theory. Instead, guide your presentation by the particular problems that animate your paper. For example, if you are writing in criticism of John Rawls's "difference principle," you should not try to sketch his theory of the original position and the argument for the principle within the original position. Confine yourself with the aspects of Rawls's view that are of immediate relevance to his account of fair distribution. Anything else will be a distraction and, in the short space available, is not likely to be done well.

Do not lead with (or conclude with, or otherwise include) such sweeping generalities as: "Rawls's theory of justice is the most important recent contribution to the perennial human search for the ideal society," or "Since Plato, philosophers have sought out the meaning of justice," or "For millennia, human beings have searched for truth," or "Philosophy is based on reason, not rhetoric." What about: "Man is born free, but is everywhere in chains." If you are Jean-Jacques Rousseau, you are allowed to break any rule that I have stated here. Such remarks add nothing of substance; indeed, they subtract by distracting from the issues at hand. Moreover, they suggest that the writer is unsure what to say and is looking for a way to fill some space. You do not want to create that suspicion. So just get right to the point.

Write clearly: That is easier said than done and hard to make operational. But you can make the first step by writing short sentences, avoiding page-long paragraphs, and being careful to signal transitions. Operationally: If a sentence occupies more than (say) five lines, find a way to divide it up; if a paragraph goes on for more than 20 lines, find a way to divide it up; if your paper falls into sections, make sure to include a sentence or two of connective tissue between the sections. Moreover, put things as simple as you can. Writing philosophy does not require elaborate formulations, esoteric words, neologisms, or polysyllabophilia. In a poetry course, the rules are different, but in this prosaic course, your writing should focus readers' attention on the ideas you wish to express, not on the words you have chosen to express those ideas.

Do not make the writing boring and clumsy: Introduce some stylistic variety. For example, do not start every sentence with the subject. Moreover, stay away from passive constructions: instead of "The wheel was invented by Joe," why not: "Joe invented the wheel." Do not have too many sentences that begin "It is..." or "There is..." Though such constructions are sometimes appropriate, overusing them slows things down. Avoid long strings of prepositional clauses. And try not to repeat the same words.

Support assertions: When you attribute views to the person whose ideas you are addressing, indicate the evidence for the attribution by noting relevant passages. However, you need not include quotations. As a general rule, you should only quote a passage if the passage plays an important role in the paper (say, it is a passage that you will want to be able to refer back to at various points in the argument), or if you think that there is some controversy about whether

the philosopher actually held the view you are attributing to him or her. Do not submit a paper that strings together lots of quotations.

Take the views you are discussing seriously: The political philosophers we are reading are not fools. If, as you describe the relevant parts of their views, you find yourself attributing foolish views to them, assume you have misinterpreted (perhaps you have not. But treat “misinterpretation” as the default setting.) One strategy for taking a view seriously is to “argue against yourself” when you make a criticism: ask yourself how the philosopher you are criticizing would respond to your criticism. Try to get “inside” the conception you are discussing; develop a sense of its internal integrity and see if you are able to understand how someone (who may have strange ideas but is neither moron nor sociopath) might have come to hold the views in question. The books and articles we are reading are the product of sustained reflection over a long period. The authors often distributed drafts of their manuscripts to other people and then tried to incorporate responses to the objections they received. The result is not that their views are right, or genuinely coherent, or nice. However, you can safely assume that they have greater depth and coherence than you may suspect on first reading.

When you finish writing, read your paper out loud. Writing that does not sound right will not read right.

In high school, you were probably told not to use the first person singular. Forget that piece of bad advice. (“In this paper, I will argue that...” is fine. “The author of this paper will argue that...” is not fine. “In this paper, it will be argued that...” is also not fine).

Do not plagiarize: Plagiarism comes in two forms, both unacceptable. First, you plagiarize when you use the words of a source without quotation marks. If you take words from a source, you must use quotation marks, not just a footnote. Moreover, you should not present a close paraphrase from a source: either use the exact words with quotation marks or restate the point in your own words.

Second, you plagiarize if you take ideas from a source without footnoting the source. Sanctions for plagiarism depend on its severity and may range from lower grades on an assignment to a failing grade for the course.

Applying these rules of thumb will require that you spend some time editing your own prose. However, the additional time will be worth it. Your papers for this course will be better than they would otherwise be, and you will eventually start to edit as you write.

NB: If you are concerned about your writing, make an appointment with the writing tutors who have been assigned to the course. Small investments of time can produce important results.

2) CHAPTER TWO: PUNCTUATIONS

Know all the punctuation marks and their usage

Learn the examples of how punctuation marks are used

Differentiate between correct and incorrect punctuations

General rule

Use as little punctuation as necessary while retaining the meaning of the sentence.

Apostrophe

to indicate possession

Use 's after singular nouns, plural nouns which do not end in s, and indefinite pronouns.

- ✓ Frank's book
- ✓ anybody's guess
- ✓ The children's play area is next to the men's toilet.

Use just ' after plural nouns ending in s.

- ✓ Strong tea is sometimes called builders' tea.

If a name already ends in s or z and would be difficult to pronounce if 's were added to the end, consider rearranging the sentence to avoid the difficulty.

- ✓ Jesus's methods were unpopular with the ruling classes. OR
The methods of Jesus were unpopular with the ruling classes.

In compound nouns and where multiple nouns are linked to make one concept, place the apostrophe at the end of the final part (and match it to that noun).

- ✓ the Archbishop of Canterbury's tortoise
- ✓ my mother-in-law's dog
- ✓ his step-brothers' cars
- ✓ Lee and Herring's *Fist of Fun*

Do not use an apostrophe in **its** with the meaning 'belonging to it' (this is analogous with his/hers/theirs): note that **it's** is a contraction of 'it is.'

- ✓ The cat has been out in the rain and its paws are muddy.
- ✓ The cat has been out in the rain and it's muddy.
- ✗ The cat has been out in the rain and it's tail is wet.

Some place names have an apostrophe, and some don't – this can't be predicted and must be checked.

- ✓ All Souls College
- ✓ Earls Court
- ✓ St Peter's College
- ✓ Land's End
- ✓ University of St Andrews

Some street names have an apostrophe (usually linked to saints' names from nearby churches); these are also idiosyncratic.

- ✓ There is a famous pub on St Giles'.
- ✗ St Giles's splits into Woodstock and Banbury Roads.
- ✓ Christ Church is on St Aldate's.
- ✓ St Michael's Street is a through road for bicycles.

Use apostrophes with noun phrases denoting periods (use an apostrophe if you can replace the apostrophe with 'of').

- ✓ He took a week's holiday [holiday of a week].
- ✓ You must give three months' notice [notice of three months].

But do not use an apostrophe in adjectival phrases.

- ✓ She was eight months pregnant when she went into labor.

Apostrophe (cont)

to indicate that letters have been omitted (contractions)

Use an apostrophe in the position the omitted letters would have occupied, not where the space was between the original words.

✓ I don't like cheese. [=do not]

✗ I do'nt like cheese. [≠do not]

✓ He wouldn't do that.

Do not use an apostrophe before contractions are accepted as words in their own right.

✓ He is on the phone.

✓ He had swine flu.

✗ There is no vaccine for all types of 'flu.

Do not use an apostrophe to make a plural, even with a word/phrase that is not usually written in the plural or which appears clunky. All of the following examples take an **s** as normal in English to make their plurals.

✗ Three video's for a tenner.

✗ I trust all the MP's.

✗ Clothes were colorful in the 1970's.

✗ CD's will soon be obsolete.

✗ This is a list of do's and don't's.

To clarify something that looks odd if an **s** is added, consider italicizing it or placing it in single quotation marks.

✓ Subtract all the *x*s from the *y*s.

✓ Dot the 'i's and cross the 't's.

Brackets

round brackets ()

Use in place of a pair of dashes or commas around a non-defining phrase (one which adds extra information, a translation, dates, an explanation, or a definition).

✓ The library (which was built in the seventeenth century) needs to be repaired.

✓ It was (as far as I could tell) the only example of its kind.

✓ Magdalen College (founded in 1458) has a herd of deer.

✓ The tactic of *Blitzkrieg* (which means 'lightning war' in German) was used in the invasion of Poland in 1939.

✓ Preheat the oven to 350°F (180°C).

using other punctuation with brackets

Include full stops/exclamation marks/question marks/quotation marks before the closing bracket only if the complete sentence/quote is in brackets; otherwise, punctuate after the closing bracket.

✓ The last bus today is at 4.45 (which is earlier than usual).

✓ The last bus today is at 4.45. (That's earlier than usual.)

square brackets []

Use to enclose comments, corrections, references, or translations made by a subsequent author or editor.

✓ An article referring to the restrictions placed by some airlines on the appearance of female cabin crew stated that even footwear was proscribed [sic].

✓ I have been responsible in the real sense, that I have had the blame for everything that has gone wrong. [Laughter and cheers.]

✓ This was quoted by Brown [1940, Chicago].

angle brackets < > and curly brackets { }

These are used for technical purposes – only use them in the correct context.

Bullet points

Don't punctuate the end of bullet points which are a list of items.

- ✔ 2014 concert performers:
 - Slade
 - The Smiths
 - Metallica
 - the Spice Girls

If the bullet points form a complete sentence with preceding text, add a full stop to the end of the last point.

- ✔ We are holding a concert in 2014, at which the following acts will perform:
 - Slade
 - The Smiths
 - Metallica
 - the Spice Girls.

If text inside the bullet point is a complete sentence in its own right, add a semicolon to the end of each point, 'or' or 'and' (depending on the sense of your sentence) to the end of the penultimate point, and a full stop to the end of the last one.

- ✔ The following will be considered good reasons for missing the final meeting of the year:
 - there was a postal strike. This only applies if the postal strike took place before the date of the meeting and if you have not signed up for email alerts;
 - you are absent as a result of illness;
 - you are unable to attend because of problems with public transport (proof of this will be required);
 - there is something more interesting happening elsewhere which you would rather attend; or
 - you have obtained a ticket to see the Spice Girls in concert.

Colon and semicolon

Use a colon to introduce a subclause that follows logically from the text before it, is not a new concept, and depends logically on the preceding main clause.

- ✔ When I was young, I went on two holidays: to the Lake District and to Cornwall.
- ✔ A new drink was introduced to Britain: tea.

Do not use a colon if the two parts of the sentence are not logically connected.

- ✘ I used to be slim: I will try to lose weight.
- ✔ I would like to be slim: I will try to lose weight.
- ✘ We were in trouble this time: we'd never been in trouble before.
- ✔ We were in trouble this time: the lid had come right off.
- ✔ There are two parts to this sentence: the first part, which precedes the colon, and the second part, which doesn't.

Use a semicolon to link two related parts of a sentence, neither of which depends logically on the other and each of which could stand alone as a grammatically complete sentence.

- ✔ The best job is the one you enjoy; the worst job is the one you hate.
- ✔ It is a far, far better thing that I do, than I have ever done; it is a far, far better rest that I go to, than I have ever known.

Use semicolons in place of commas in a complicated list or sentence if it will improve clarity, particularly if list items already include commas.

- ✔ We plan to review the quality of the research of the department, including its participation in interdepartmental, interdivisional and interdisciplinary activities; its research profile and strategy; and future challenges and opportunities.
- ✔ I visited the Ashmolean Museum, Oxford; the Victoria and Albert Museum, London; and the Pencil Museum, Keswick.

Comma

Use a pair of commas to surround a non-defining clause (one which adds descriptive information but which can be removed without losing the meaning of the sentence) – note that only ‘which’ or ‘who’ can be used in this type of clause, not ‘that.’

- ✔ The library, which was built in the seventeenth century, needs to be repaired.
- ✔ The man, who climbed the tower without a safety harness, died of old age.

Do not use commas to surround a defining clause (which cannot be removed without losing the sentence's meaning) – note that ‘which’ or ‘who’ can be replaced by ‘that’ in this type of clause.

- ✔ The library which was built in the seventeenth century needs to be repaired [but the library which was built in the eighteenth century does not].
- ✔ The man that climbed the tower without a safety harness died of old age [but the other man died in a different way].
- ✔ He asked his friend Sam to be his second [not any of his other friends].

Use commas to surround a non-defining word or phrase (which adds information but could be omitted without changing the sense of the sentence), and follow the non-defining word/phrase with a single comma if it is at the start of the sentence.

- ✔ Shakespeare, the prolific playwright, might not have existed.
- ✔ A prolific playwright, Shakespeare might not have existed.
- ✔ He asked Sam, his friend, to be his second [not the Sam who is his barber].
- ✔ The prime minister, David Cameron, is an alumnus of Brasenose.

Do not use a comma where defining information is used at the start of a sentence.

- ✔ The prolific playwright Shakespeare might not have existed.
- ✘ The prolific playwright, Shakespeare might not have existed.
- ✔ His friend Sam was his second.
- ✘ His friend, Sam was his second.

Defining vs. non-defining information

Do not use a comma to join two main clauses or those linked by adverbs or adverbial phrases (e.g., ‘nevertheless,’ ‘therefore,’ ‘however’). This is sometimes referred to as ‘comma splicing.’ Either use a semicolon or add a coordinating conjunction (e.g. ‘and,’ ‘but,’ ‘so’).

- ✔ Shakespeare was popular, and his plays were all profitable.
- ✔ Shakespeare was popular; his plays were all profitable.
- ✘ Shakespeare was popular, his plays were all profitable.

Use a comma after an introductory adverb, adverbial phrase, or subordinate clause, or use a pair of commas surrounding it if it is in the middle of a sentence.

- ✔ However, it was too late for that.
- ✔ It was, however, too late for that.
- ✔ With his possessions in a bundle, Dick Whittington walked to London.
- ✔ Dick Whittington, with his possessions in a bundle, walked to London.

Do not use a comma after a time-based adverbial phrase.

- ✔ After playing tennis all day she was tired.
- ✔ Whenever she went to the cinema she ate popcorn.
- ✔ In 2010 the most popular game among children was hopscotch.

Use a comma between multiple qualitative adjectives (those which can be used in the comparative/superlative or modified with ‘very,’ ‘quite,’ etc.).

- ✔ He was a big, fat, sweaty man with soft, wet hands.

Do not use a comma between multiple classifying adjectives: absolutes which either are or are not, such as 'unique,' 'English,' 'black,' etc. (although note that stylistically these can be modified).

✔ It was an edible German mushroom.

✔ The eighteenth-century sandstone tower is lit up at night.

Do not use a comma between classifying and qualitative adjectives.

✔ It was a large German mushroom with hard black edges.

✔ It was a large, squishy German mushroom with hard, frilly black edges.

Use a comma between items in a list.

✔ I ate fish, bread, ice cream and spaghetti.

✔ I have nothing to offer but blood, toil, tears and sweat.

Note that there is no comma between the penultimate item in a list and 'and'/'or', unless required to prevent ambiguity – this is sometimes referred to as the 'Oxford comma.' However, always insert a comma in this position if it would help prevent confusion.

✘ He took French, Spanish, and Maths A-levels.

✔ I ate fish and chips, bread and jam, and ice cream.

✔ We studied George III, William and Mary, and Henry VIII.

✘ She left her money to her parents, Mother Theresa and the pope.

Dashes and hyphens — - -

m-dash (—)

Do not use; use an n-dash instead.

n-dash (–)

Use in a pair in place of round brackets or commas, surrounded by spaces.

✔ It was – as far as I could tell – the only example of its kind.

✔ The library – which was built in the seventeenth century – needs to be repaired.

Use singly and surrounded by spaces to link two parts of a sentence in place of a colon.

✔ The bus was late today – we nearly missed the lecture.

Use to link concepts or ranges of numbers, with no spaces either side.

✔ German–Polish non-aggression pact

✔ The salary for the post is £25,000–£30,000.

✔ Radio 1 is aimed at the 18–25 age bracket.

Use between names of joint authors/creators/performers etc to distinguish from hyphenated names of a single person.

✔ Lennon–McCartney compositions

✔ Superman–Batman crossover comics

hyphen (-)

When to use a hyphen

In an adjectival phrase before a noun

- ✓ the up-to-date list
- ✓ The value of a first-class degree is indisputable.
- ✓ a hot-air balloon
- ✓ 'Rethinking provincialism in mid-nineteenth-century narrative fiction: Villette from our village'

In an adjectival phrase including a verb participle

- ✓ The jumper was tight-fitting.

With prefixes only if required to avoid confusion/mispronunciation, such as where prefixes themselves or letters are repeated

- ✓ predynastic Egypt
- ✓ gifts of pre-eminent objects and works of art to the nation
- ✓ The animals are re-released into the wild when recovered.
- ✓ A protein precursor can also be called a pro-protein.
- ✓ Procapitalists and anticapitalists clashed in the streets.
- ✓ The email address for the webmaster can be found on the website.

With prefixes before a proper name, number or date

- ✓ anti-Thatcherism
- ✓ pre-2000 politics
- ✓ Hilary term starts in mid-January.

In numbers which are spelled out

- ✓ Twenty-seven is the most popular 'random' number.
- ✓ *The Thirty-Nine Steps*

In compass points (unless used geographically rather than as directions)

- ✓ They're heading south-east.
- ✓ nor'-nor'-east
- ✓ The southwest is a popular holiday destination.

When not to use a hyphen

In noun phrases

- ✓ Labour Party conference
- ✓ The 19th century saw much reform.

To make a new compound noun – if it is a recognisable concept, make it one word; if it isn't, use two words

- ✓ Websites are made up of webpages.
- ✓ Send me an email when you're ready to proceed.
- ✗ Send me an e-mail.

In an adjectival phrase following a noun

- ✓ The list was up to date.
- ✓ His marks just scraped into the first class.
- ✗ She wasn't top-drawer.

In an adjectival phrase before a noun where the first element is an adverb ending in -ly (but note that any other adverbs in adjectival phrases do take a hyphen)

- ✓ She had a finely tuned ear for off-key music.
- ✓ XML documents must be well-formed texts.
- ✗ She was a highly-respected tutor.
- ✓ She was a badly paid apprentice.

Ellipsis...

Use an ellipsis to show that some text is missing, usually from a quotation – do not surround it with spaces.

✔ ...we shall fight on the beaches...we shall never

✔ surrender... It is a truth universally acknowledged...

There is no need to add square brackets around an ellipsis.

✘ [...] we shall fight on the beaches [...]

Use an ellipsis to indicate a pause for comic or other effects – follow the ellipsis with a space in this case, as it stands in place of a comma or full stop.

✔ You don't have to be mad to work here... but it helps!

Note that, if used either in place of omitted text at the end of a clause/sentence or to indicate a pause for effect, a full stop/comma should not follow the ellipsis. However, an exclamation mark or a question mark can and should follow the ellipsis if required.

✔ Are you...?

✔ Did he say that...?

Use an ellipsis to indicate a trailing off in speech or thought.

✔ We could do this...or maybe that...

Full stop, exclamation mark, and question mark

Use one – but only one – of these at the end of every sentence.

✔ What time did you leave last night?

✔ We went home at 5 o'clock.

✔ Go home now!

Do not use a full stop at the end of titles, even if they make a sentence, but if a title ends with an exclamation mark or question mark, do include it.

✔ *All's Well that Ends Well* is my favorite play.

✔ 'Will You Still Love Me Tomorrow?' was a hit for the Shirelles.

✔ 'Help!' was covered by Bananarama in 1989.

Do not use a full stop if it will be followed or preceded by an ellipsis.

✘ Behind him stood a figure. ...It was ghostly grey.

Use a full stop, not a question mark, at the end of a reported question – only use a question mark for a direct question (whether in quotation marks or not).

✔ He asked if I wanted to go home that morning.

✔ 'Do you want to go home this morning?' he

✘ asked. He asked if I wanted to go home?

Use a full stop, not an exclamation mark, at the end of a reported imperative.

✔ Wait for me! He asked me to wait for him.

Quotation marks

Use single quotation marks for direct speech or a quote and double quotation marks for direct speech or a quote within that.

✔ 'I have never been to Norway,' he said, 'but I have heard it described as "the Wales of the North".'

Use no quotation marks if the quote is displayed (i.e., not in line with the rest of the text).

✔ as I noted then,
Those of us who toil in the Groves of Academe
know full well that our research helps inform
our teaching...

Use single quotation marks and roman (not italic) type for titles that are not whole publications: e.g. short poems, short stories, songs, chapters in books, articles in periodicals etc. See also **Highlighting/emphasizing text**.

✔ *I, Robot* contains nine short stories, of which 'Little Lost Robot' is my favorite.

✔ Queen's 'Bohemian Rhapsody,' from the album *Night at the Opera*, reached number one in both 1975 and 1991.

Using other punctuation with quotation marks

If the quote would have required punctuation in its original form, place the punctuation inside the quotation marks. (If it is unclear, try writing the whole sentence out without quotation marks and 'he said' etc., and replicate the resulting punctuation.)

✔ Bob likes cheese. 'Bob,' I said, 'likes cheese.' OR
'Bob likes cheese,' I said.

✔ Bob, do you like cheese? 'Bob,' I asked, 'do you like cheese?'

✔ Out, damn'd spot! 'Out,' said Lady Macbeth, 'damn'd spot!' 'You're

✔ engaged to Florence?' I yipped, looking at him with a wild surmise.

Place any punctuation which does not belong to the quote outside the quotation marks (except closing punctuation if the end of the quote is also the end of the sentence).

✔ After all, tomorrow is another day. 'After all,' said Scarlett, 'tomorrow is another day.' OR
'After all, tomorrow,' said Scarlett, 'is another day.'

✘ 'The kitchen,' he said, 'is the heart of the home.'

✔ 'The kitchen,' he said, 'is the heart of the home.'

Note that American English has different rules about the use of quotation marks.

3) CHAPTER THREE: AMERICAN VS. BRITISH ENGLISH

Understand US English

Understand UK English

Understand the differences between US & UK English

Introduction

American English has grown steadily in international significance since World War II, parallel to the growth of U.S. political, economic, technological, and cultural influence worldwide. American English is currently the dominant influence on "world English" (cf. British English) largely due to the following:

1. Population: U.S. vs. U.K. (SAE/SBE ca 70% vs. 17% of all native English)
2. Wealth of the U.S. economy vs. the U.K., and influences
3. The magnitude of higher education in America vs. the U.K.
4. The magnitude of the publishing industry in America
5. Magnitude of global mass media and media technology influence
6. The appeal of American popular culture on language and habits
7. The international political and economic position of the U.S.

American and British English are both variants of World English. As such, they are more similar than different, especially with "educated" or "scientific" English. Most divergence can be ascribed to differing national histories and cultural development (cf. *Are Americans Ruining English?* [PBS]) and the way in which the two national variants have changed correspondingly.

The following general categories of difference between standard American English (SAE) and standard British English (SBE) each have their sociolectic value:

Different Pronunciation, Although Same Spelling

Advertisement (advert, ad)

Controversy, laboratory, secretary, leisure, schedule, dynasty, dance

Renaissance, oregano, migratory, clerk [bank, office], ate

'PC'-influence problematics: harass & harassment, Uranus, etc. (Consistency? Predictability? — cf. 'horehound,' etc.)

Different Spelling, Although Same Pronunciation

Axe — ax; plough — plow; colour — color, centre — center

Cheque — check (noun form [bank]; the verb "to check" the same) Defence — defense (noun form), licence (noun form) — license Alright — all right; manoeuvre — maneuver; tyre — tire

Ageing — aging; gaol — jail

Same Term, Different but Similar Spelling and Pronunciation

Aluminium — aluminum

Polythene — polyethylene

Maths — math (shortening of "mathematics")

Rise — raise (more money in salary, wages)

Same Words, But Different or Additional Meanings

I married a homely girl. The opening of our new play was a bomb!

We all had tea and biscuits. (cf. Harry Potter, 'crumpets' vs. 'English muffins,' etc.) The corn harvest was exceptional this year.

(cf. US "maize" or "sweetcorn;" GB "any cereal" or "wheat," Scotland "oats," etc.; cf. example)

We needed a torch for the dark trail. (cf. flashlight, or GB 'electric torch,' flaming torch) IBM made over a billion dollars last year. (cf. "thousand million;" 'changing' GB standards)

The committee tabled the motion (GB: put it on the table).

Nigel and Trevor purchased 7-day Travelcard season tickets. Ralph needs to write an essay for his university course.

GB 'trousers' = US 'pants'; US 'pants' = GB 'underwear pants'

(cf. 'It was a tremendous storm; when it was over my pants were all wet')

Grammar, Syntax, Punctuation, General Usage

Date writing, number/word order (never use only numbers!) Use of commas and periods inside quotation marks

Business letter salutations, colons vs. commas

'Honorifics:' Mr. or Mrs. or Dr. Smith (U.S.) vs. Mr or Mrs or Dr. Smith (GB), etc.

Differences in Usage with SBE 'Large Collective Nouns'

(U.S.) Finnair has a flight to London today. (G.B.) Finnair have a flight to London today.

(U.S.) England has (...) played well today, even if it lost. (G.B.) England have played well today, even if they lost.

(G.B.) The Government are acting like themselves again.

Differences in Usage with SBE 'Pluralised Adjectives'

SAE: John failed his drug test and will be excluded from the team. SBE: John failed his drugs test and will be excluded from the team.

Cf. also the British "appointments book", "drinks counter", and "careers guidance"

However, there is also SBE "book shop", "magazine rack" and "student meeting", etc.; usage varies with both instance and individual usage.

Usage also varies in SBE internationally (e.g., local adaptations?) cf. SAE: I purchased my new sandals from the shoe store on Mombasa Road SBE: I purchased my new sandals from the shoes store on Mombasa Road.

Other Common Usage Differences

(G.B.) Have you got your grade in history yet? (U.S.) Have you gotten your grade in history yet?

(G.B.) He went on a course. How many were on the course? (U.S.) He was in a course. How many were in the course?

(G.B.) We lived in the High Street. (cf 'street people' ...)

(U.S.) We lived on Main Street ("on" plus article plus High/Main)

(G.B.) He's in the hospital with a broken leg. (U.S.) He's in the hospital with a broken leg.

(G.B.) I have got a car. vs. (U.S.) I have a car. I got a car. (different implications)

(G.B.) We weren't able to catch him up

(U.S.) We weren't able to catch him, catch up with him, catch up [with him].

One was different from/than the other.

Same Concept, Different Terms or Expressions; (or) Same Word, Differences in Style, Connotation and Frequency

Hire a car — rent a car (hire-purchase vs. installment plan)

Petrol — gasoline; Saloon — sedan, Estate car — station wagon

Boot — trunk (storage area); silencer — muffler (to reduce exhaust noise); other auto terms

Fortnight — two weeks; Goods train — freight train

Barrister vs. solicitor ['brief,' 'silk'] — lawyer, attorney, attorney-at-law

Sweet (vs. "sweets") — dessert; red whortleberries — lingonberries, food terminology generally (see 'Localizations' of Food Terms in Children's Books)

GB "bank holiday" vs US "public holiday" or just "holiday"; "Boxing Day"

GB "mates" & "lads" vs US "friends"; GB "tossers" & "wankers" vs US "dorks" & "losers" etc.

"Could you tell me where Waterloo Station is?" (UK); "Would you be able to use one of these?" (AU);

"yes/no" vs. expected cultural response

See also Lost in Translation for US/GB 'changeability' [quite or very?] and other examples

"Creativity": Spinoffs; Combos; Referencing of Current Events and Brands

Hamburger — cheeseburger, beefburger, fishburger, lobsterburger... Hotel, motel, floatel, boatel

Hardware, software, firmware, shareware, freeware, vaporware, "treeware"

Suburb, exurb, technoburb, cyburb — citizen, netizen — atmosphere, blogosphere
Copyright to "copyleft" (cf. 'Wiki' contributions, for example), 'to Google', 'googling'

Verify to "wherify" (use of GPS-locator technology with children)

Twitter & 'twittering,' twitterati, twittiquette, a 'tweet' — (cf. The Twictionary)

"Climate canary," "to be YouTubed, to be Plutoed" (cf. [WOTY2006 \[PDF\]](#)), a "plutoid" ['something less than a planet'], etc.

The "boingg" effect (cf. 'sproingg,' etc.) (**N.E. Journal of Medicine** 1981, then 21st century)

Fashionista, stylista, frugalista, accessorista (all reflective of both the present economic situation and new 'Spanglish' influence)

Smoke/fog = smog; cf. cosmetics/pharmaceuticals = cosmeceuticals;
pharmaceuticals/farming = pharming

'Brand name' recognition — cf. "Half and half"; "A six-pack of PBR tallboys"

(Roz, on *Frasier*): "I'm going to climb into a hot tub with my good friends Ben and Jerry"

Euphemistic References

Security officer, hair stylist, household manager

Powder room, ladies' lounge; motion discomfort bag

A "pre-owned" car (cf "used car" & "used-car salesman")

"The loved one..." (cf. [death and funeral references](#) generally)

"To deselect, dehire" employees; to "downsize, right-size" the company

"Equality" Vocabulary

Fireman/firefighter, policeman/police officer, mailman/mail carrier Stewardess/flight attendant, salesman/salesperson, etc.

Chairman — chairperson, chair, presiding officer Manmade — artificial, synthetic, manufactured

"Politically Correct" References

Seniors; 'older' adults (55 & older) vs. "elderly" or "old" people

African Americans vs. 'black Americans' or 'blacks' or 'people of color' 'Stay-at-home mom' vs. "housewife" (not 'married to one's house')

"Canola" vs. "rapeseed" oil; animal companion vs. "pet," Native American vs. "Indian" Recent controversies: an 'articulate' black politician? A niggardly budget?

'Ethnolects': "Black English" (specific terminology in cultural context)

Everybody look down at the feet; I ain't afraid of nuthin' You ugly, man; I the baddest cat around; He be good.

Boy, nigger, soul food, honkie, rapping (note the disagreement over the term)

Yiddish and Ethnic Jewish Influence (lexical & structural) on SAE

Schlep, goy, schlemiel, schlock, chutzpa, nebbish, shtik

I should have such luck! He's complaining yet! This I need? What's not to like?

"Schm-/shm' reduplication," from the Yiddish *koyfn*, *shmoyfn* (to buy, not to buy; who cares?) e.g., 'fat-shmat, so long as she's happy,' 'fancy-schmancy' (pretentious) or 'Oedipus, schmoedipus — as long as he loves his mother!')

Various Jargons; Changing Cultural References...

Computer culture: fonts, multitasking, up/downloading, blogging, lurking, flaming, etc.

Technoculture: technocrat, technopeasant, techno-potato; a virtual corporation

Infoculture: telecommuting, edutainment, 'terrestrial' TV (vs cable, satellite); [broadcasting to] 'narrowcasting', broadband vs narrowband, digital vs analogue watches

"Gay" culture: (drag, closet, fairy, fruitcake, 'to out' — 'he was outed') [vs GB 'poof', etc.]

Drugs: Cocaine (coke, leaf, snow, angel dust); crack, valise, kilos, brick, 'trips'

Social 'Trendiness' (status): Yuppie, Buppie, Puppie, Dinks, Woofs

Business: Power breakfast, Valium picnic, warm fuzzies

Youthisms: dork, nerd, geek, dweeb; psyched, pumped, barf

Regional Variation, Identity, Stereotyping

i) *Variation in Terminology*

Soda vs. Soda Pop vs. Pop vs. Coke vs. 'tonic,' etc. (see map from www.popvssoda.com)
'Ice cream soda' vs. 'milk shake' vs. 'shake' vs. frappe vs. cabinet

'Rubber band' vs. 'gumband' (Pittsburgh region), etc.

Terms for general, 'anonymous' or 'stereotypical' persons

"Uncle Sam" (U.S.) vs. "John Bull" (U.K.)

John Doe, John Q. Public, Joe Citizen, Joe Senior

Joe Blow, Joe Shmoe, Joe Six-Pack, "brother," "sister"

"Southern" names: Billy Bob, Jimmy Joe, Bubba, and Beauregard

Varying implications (region, education, ethnic) of "non-grammatical" language

(a) "He ain't done nothin' yet" (uneducated, rural?)

(b) "He done et over at th' Hatfields" (hillbilly...)

(c) "You be late...the food be cold." (Black English)

"Four-letter words," Obscenities and Implied Obscenities

Damn, fart, piss, crap, turd, shit, fuck, cunt; vs. GB bloody, bugger, bollocks, sod, tosser, etc.

Examples of Differences with Punctuation and Dates

The Writing of Dates

08/07/60 vs. 08.07.60 or 080760, etc.

(Are different expression styles recognizable? Is the date August 7 or July 8?) "2008-09-15" is the ISO 8601 standard, esp. in technical fields

08 July 1960 July 8, 1960

(July the 8th, 1960, etc.)

Periods, Commas, and Quotation Marks

THIS IS EXTREMELY IMPORTANT!

'The boy kicked the ball.' (GB 'inverted commas') "The boy kicked the ball." (US "quotation marks")

(cf. Neea Paatero's 'Gatsby' analysis for UK/US punctuation differences)

'She screamed, "I didn't do it!" and then ran away.' (GB format, quotation within a quotation)

"She screamed, 'I didn't do it!' and then ran away." (US format, - - -)

He said, 'I didn't like what they had for dessert.'

(FIN/GB variable procedure for periods & commas in quotations, where the period/comma may be either inside or outside closing quotation marks)

He said, "I didn't like what they had for dessert."

(US fixed standard, where periods & commas are always inside closing quotation marks)

Punctuation with Business (Formal) vs. Social (Informal) Letters

Dear Mr Smith, (GB) Dear Aunt Sally, (GB)

Dear Mr. Smith: (US) — (also note the GB "Mr" vs. the US "Mr.")

To Whom It May Concern: (US) Dear Aunt Sally, (GB)

4) CHAPTER FOUR: PLAGIARISM

Know what plagiarism is and how to avoid it

Know how/when to cite and paraphrase

Be able to insert footnotes using MS Word

When writing papers, one of the most important things the writer should do is avoid Plagiarism.

What is Plagiarism?

Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information.

Examples of Plagiarism

Taking someone else's words or ideas, such as quoting, paraphrasing, copying, and pasting from the internet and not giving credit to the author. Having someone write a paper for you and then putting your name on it and giving it to your professor would be plagiarism.

When to Give Credit to Author?

When using any quote, paraphrase, statistic/data, or visuals (such as a graph) that is borrowed from another source.

Why Mention the Source?

Why should anyone bother mentioning the source of where the information they are writing about

came from? What is the harm?

- Plagiarism is wrong and unethical
- It is not fair to take someone's work and not give them credit
- It is a serious academic offense that can have serious consequences

So How do we Avoid Plagiarism?

In order to avoid plagiarism, the solution is to properly CITE the author or source that has provided the information you are using.

How to Cite/What Does it Mean to Cite?

Method used to indicate where a piece of information came from.

There are two things about citing you will need to be aware of.

- A. There are in-text citations, and
- B. List of works cited.

i) *In-Text Citation*

Refers to citing the piece of work you are using within the actual text itself. For example, “Before 1984, footnotes and endnotes were used in research reports. In certain instances, this form of documentation is still correct” (Gerson and Gerson 143).

In the above example, the parenthesis indicates the authors who wrote the passage and the page that this material came from – page 143. This is how you would cite a source of information.

So, the above example shows that when you cite something in the text of your paper, you simply need to put the author's name in parenthesis with the page number that the information came from.

So, what are some of the more common things we would like to cite using this method?

- A. Quotations
- B. Paraphrases

ii) *What are Quotations?*

Are the exact words of an author.

When you use a quotation, you must use quotation marks “.....” to capture what the author has said.

How to cite quotations? Use the same method discussed above. Put the author’s name in parenthesis followed by the page number:

In the technical communication process and product, it is mentioned that “Before 1984, footnotes and endnotes were used in research reports. In certain instances, this form of documentation is still correct” (Gerson and Gerson 143).

Long Quotations

Long quotations take a different look. Quotations that are over four lines will be treated a little

differently:

- A. They will take no quotation marks (“”)
- B. They will be indented and look like separate little paragraphs. In the EUCLID template, use the Quote Style

Long Quotation Example

Joyce Williams, in her book, *Lizzie Borden: A Case Book of Family and Crime in the 1890s*, mentions the following:

The rise of industry, the growth of cities, and the expansion of the population were the three great developments of late nineteenth century American history. As new, larger, steam powered factories became a feature of the American landscape in the East, they transformed farm hands into industrial laborers and provided jobs for a rising tide of immigrants. With industry came urbanization the growth of large cities (like Fall River, Massachusetts, where the Bordens lived) which became the centers of production as well as of commerce and trade.

iii) *A Few Tips about Quotations*

- Limit the use of quotations. If you use it too much, it does not look like your own research.
- Use quotations when there is especially strong language in the quote that emphasizes the meaning very well.
- Use quotations when an authority figure says something that can help you persuade the reader.

iv) *Paraphrases*

Paraphrases are the ideas and information that an author has produced on a topic but written in your own words.

In a paper, it does not look very good if you have too many quotes. So, you will need to paraphrase at times.

The paraphrase you use must look very different than how the author originally wrote it.

A. Must be YOUR words. The language you use cannot resemble the words of the author. So, this means you cannot just change a couple of words and rearrange the sentence structure

B. The writing style you use to express the author's ideas must be different from the style the author used

C. The information that you are providing must be an accurate representation of what the author originally wrote

D. Finally, after doing all and indicating where the source of the above, you must still CITE the work information came from

Examples of Paraphrasing I

Here is the ORIGINAL text, from page 1 of *Lizzie Borden: A Case Book of Family and Crime in the 1890s* by Joyce Williams et al.:

The rise of industry, the growth of cities, and the expansion of the population were the three great developments of late nineteenth century American history. As new, larger, steam-powered factories became a feature of the American landscape in the East; they transformed farm hands into industrial laborers and provided jobs for a rising tide of immigrants. With industry came urbanization the growth of large cities (like Fall River, Massachusetts, where the Bordens lived) which became the centers of production as well as of commerce and trade (Szabist, “A Workshop on Proper Academic Referencing”, November 2006).

Examples of Paraphrasing II

The following would be an unacceptable paraphrase:

The increase of industry, the growth of cities, and the explosion of the population were three large factors of nineteenth century America. As steamdriven companies became more visible in the eastern part of the country, they changed farm hands into factory workers and provided jobs for the large wave of immigrants. With industry came the growth of large cities like Fall A river where the Bordens lived which turned into centers of commerce and trade as well as production (Szabist, “A Workshop on Proper Academic Referencing”, November 2006).

Examples of Paraphrasing III

Here is an acceptable paraphrase:

Fall River, where the Borden family lived, was typical of northeastern industrial cities of the nineteenth century. Steam-powered production had shifted labor from agriculture to manufacturing, and as immigrants arrived in the US, they found work in these new factories. As a result, populations grew, and large urban areas arose. Fall River was one of these manufacturing and commercial centers (Williams 1). (Szabist, “A Workshop on Proper Academic Referencing”, November 2006).

When NOT to Cite

We mentioned when to cite, but how about when NOT to cite? Certainly, we cannot cite everything. So, when do we not cite something?

- When the information you are writing about is common knowledge that can be found in numerous areas, you do not need to cite its source
- For example, smoking causes lung cancer. There is no need to cite since it is well known that smoking causes lung cancer
- What if you are new to a subject and you are researching a topic that you have no knowledge of, and you do not know if it is common knowledge that can easily be found in numerous places?
- The basic rule you can use is that if it is repeated in many different sources that you have you, then you can assume it is common knowledge

Signal Phrases

Using signal phrases introduces a quotation or paraphrase by using a verb and mentioning the author's name.

Gerson and Gerson point out that “Before 1984, footnotes and endnotes were used in research reports. In certain instances, this form of documentation is still correct” (143).

Notice that by using a signal phrase, “point out,” we were able to use the author's name in the beginning and leave out the author's name in the citation, and put only the page number in parenthesis.

List of Works Cited

- What is List of Works Cited?
- It is the ‘bibliography’ or the ‘references’ listed at the end of the book
- It provides publication information for each of the sources that were cited in the paper

Format to Follow

There are a few basic formats that are to be followed

For books, use the following format:

Authors Name. Date. Book Title. Place of Publication: Publisher.

For example:

Gerson, Steven. 2009. *Technical Communication Process and Product*. Upper Saddle River: Pearson.

NB: Often, the title is italicized (not underlined)

Online Works

- For online books, referenced the same way as a book
- For a website: Author. Title of the site, name of any editors listed, date the URL was accessed, and the URL in brackets (<URL>)

Footnote Referencing Part 1

- Make your citation either in the sentence between “” or as a separate paragraph using the “Quote style.”

After the punctuation, click the References menu > Insert Footnote (in Word 2007 and above). Make sure that you use footnotes, not endnotes. They will automatically be numbered.

Footnote Referencing Part 2

In the footnote area, enter your reference with a standard format and be consistent. Typically, the format is:

John Perkins, *Understanding Assessment* (London: Penguin, 2008), 78.

If you use this method, you do not need to add a “Works Cited / References” at the end of your paper

More about Citations

You can only make citations with papers that you prepare independently (not supervised exams)

In a journal/response paper, we recommend making one citation

In a mid-term or final exam, we recommend making 2 or 3 citations

Personal Vs. Academic Style

Never use contractions such as “can’t” “won’t” “isn’t” etc.

Write in a formal academic style, and sometimes, provide personal examples

Find the right balance between the 2!

Academic style means (among other things), using logical connectors so that there is flow in your papers

Achieving “Logical Flow”

For longer papers, use Headings. Start with the headings (section titles) to organize your paper and then write the text inside the sections

Learn how to use “However,” “Nevertheless,” “On the one hand,” “On the other hand,” “In spite of this,” “For this reason,” “As a result,” “Moreover,” “Furthermore,” etc.

5) CHAPTER FIVE: WHAT IS A STYLE GUIDE, AND WHY WOULD I NEED ONE?

Understand what a style guide is

Why a writer needs a particular style guide

What a style guide constitutes

Note: EUCLID recommends the Chicago Rules (Turabian), but other internationally recognized Rules are fine. Please download the template and EUCLID guidelines for information on how to format the Euclid papers. EUCLID also recommends using American English, but both versions are obviously accepted.

A style guide is a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent. Style guides are generally associated with certain types of writing like technical writing, commercial or business writing, journalism, and web copywriting. In each of these cases, there is a need to ensure that the writing style is consistent. So guidelines are usually published to allow more than one author to contribute while ensuring that the finished piece does not necessarily carry the personal style of the writer but that of the publication, company, or website associated with the writing. For publications or companies with many contributing authors, a style guide is essential if the finished publication is to be coherent and consistent.

Many creative writers eschew the need for a style guide, believing that the ability to follow a standard English writing style should be an innate quality for any writer. While, to a certain extent, this could be argued to be true, a style guide provides a means of documenting basic rules or features of your writing that will allow you to ensure consistency in your written output. Technical writers, for example, will generally have a style guide for a particular customer or project to ensure that the data they deliver will be in an acceptable form and will be in keeping with previous deliveries or other publications that the customer already has.

The lack of a single authoritative source on style for written English means that there is, and will always be, a certain amount of debate on elements of style. The use of punctuation and correct grammar is well established and clear, but the style is much more than just the correct usage of punctuation, grammar, and vocabulary. Style can encompass many different aspects like:

- preferred sentence lengths
- manuscript layout
- font usage
- depth of treatment of a subject
- spelling (UK v US for example)
- readership considerations
- use of abbreviations
- accepted terminology
- the use of symbols
- voice preferences (active v passive)
- structure

- paragraph numbering and indentation
- the use of headings
- the use of lists
- trademark or branding considerations

This list could easily be longer, too, as each publication, company, or writer will view any number of elements of the style of their writing. You can see from the list that creative writers may not be worried about most of the items, whereas a bid proposal writer or a technical writer may need to heed all of the considerations in their daily work.

A style guide should be an invaluable tool for any writer, but particularly for the freelance writer. Freelance writers should continually develop style guides for each customer or publication type that they work with. It is important that, as a freelancer, you can demonstrate an ability to follow a prescribed style, but equally that you can learn and record what your customers prefer from their comments. This will help increase your customers' satisfaction in the long term and will help place you as the supplier of choice for written material or assignments.

However, what is wrong with creative writers using their style guide? Well, nothing. Can you imagine how much time it might save in proofreading and correction if a creative writer knows that they have followed a set style from the outset in certain areas?

Some good references for setting style and following conventions can be found in Strunk's 'The Elements of Style.' The Economist style guide is freely available on their website and provides style and submission guidelines for contributors to follow. The Chicago Manual of Style has an excellent website that you can subscribe to. They will also answer your specific style questions.

Lastly, not wishing to inundate you with links, try downloading the BBC News style guide and see how one of the world's foremost news and current affairs organizations (“organisations” in British English) handles its style.

6) CHAPTER SIX: CMS CRIB SHEET

Understanding the Chicago Style

Understanding the specifications of Chicago Style

Becoming familiar with some examples

Chicago Style is the style of formatting books and research papers documented in the *Chicago Manual of Style* (CMS), 2003, and Kate Turabian's *Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 1996 (both published by the University of Chicago Press). While sometimes reference is made to a "Turabian style," this is simply the Chicago style applied to research papers. Revised Fall 2006.

CMS Crib Sheet Contents

Chicago Style & Usage

- Abbreviations & Acronyms
- Capitalization
- Compound Words
- Emphasis: Italics/Quotes
- Numbers & Dates
- Quotations

Chicago Page Formatting

- Title and Text Page
- Footnotes
- Headings & Lists
- Bibliography & Tables
- Table Notes

Chicago End/Footnotes

- Authors & Books
- Journals & Newspapers
- Reports & Papers
- References & Documents
- Chicago Bibliographies

Chicago Style and Usage

Dictionaries. "For general matters of spelling, Chicago recommends using *Webster's Third New International Dictionary* and its chief abridgment, *Merriam-Webster's Collegiate Dictionary* . . . in its latest edition. If more than one spelling is given, or more than one form of the plural . . . , Chicago normally opts for the first form listed, thus aiding consistency. If, as occasionally happens, the *Collegiate* disagrees with the *Third International*, the *Collegiate* should be followed, since it represents the latest lexical research" (CMS 2003, 278).

Abbreviations

Abbreviations--other than acronyms/initialisms--are rarely used in the text, other than in tables, figure captions, in notes and references, or within parentheses. Follow these general rules:

1. *Beginning a sentence.* Never begin a sentence with a lowercase abbreviation. Begin a sentence with an acronym only if there is no reasonable way to rewrite it.
2. *Traditional forms.* A number of traditional honorifics and initials continue to be used, such as *Mr.*, *Mrs.*, *Ms.*, *Dr.*, *A.M.*, *Inc.*, *Ltd.*, and *J. S. Bach*, *E. E. Cummings*, *C. S. Lewis*.
3. *Scholarly abbreviations.* Abbreviations such as *etc.*, *e.g.*, and *i.e.* may only be used in parenthetical comments injected into your text. For example,—"various authorities support this rule (e.g., the *Chicago Manual of Style* and the *APA Publication Manual*)." They are **not** used outside parentheses; spell them out instead. For *e.g.* (exempli gratia) use *for example*; for, *etc.* (et cetera) use *and so forth*, for, *i.e.* (id est) use *that is*.

 "Abbreviations should be used only in contexts where they are clear to readers. . . . Writers and editors should monitor the number of different abbreviations used in a document; readers are trying to keep track of a large number of abbreviations, especially unfamiliar ones, will lose their way" (CMS 2003, 558).

Acronyms/Initialisms. When first used in the text, an acronym must be introduced. This is done by placing the acronym--or its source phrase--in parentheses and thereafter using just the acronym.

- The American Sociological Association (ASA) publishes several journals. The ASA also publishes a newsletter.
- The CDC (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention in Atlanta, Georgia) monitors the nation for emerging infectious diseases. The CDC established a special notification system after the hantavirus outbreak in 1993.
- *Plurals.* Write the plural form of an acronym without an apostrophe. For example, write "the Master of Business Administration (MBA) program is popular at the university because MBAs command high starting salaries."

Geographical Terms: Places & States. “Within the text, spell out the names of countries, states, counties, provinces, territories, bodies of water, mountains, and the like” (Turabian 1996, 19). “In running text, the names of states, territories, possessions, [Canadian provinces and territories, and foreign countries] should always be spelled out” (CMS 2003, 566).

1. *Prefixes.* Most prefixes to places, such as *Fort, North, Port, South*, are spelled out in the text, as suffixes such as *Peak* or *Fork*. Write North Platte, Fort Collins, Port Huron, South Bend, Long’s Peak.

2. *Postal Abbreviations.* Use postal and other abbreviations for place names in *references and notes*. However, spell out these and other address abbreviations in the text. Write: Martin Luther King Boulevard (not Martin Luther King Blvd.) William Bruce Randolph III Avenue (not W. B. Randolph Ave.), Monaco Parkway (not Monaco Pkwy.)

3. *Adjectives.* The abbreviation “U.S.” or “US” may be used as an adjective in running text but not as a noun. Either form is acceptable but be consistent throughout your text.

 “Abbreviations fully acceptable on envelopes and mailing labels should rarely be used in addresses in running text” (CMS 2003, 569).

Capitalization

Definitions. Capitalization may follow three forms: *full caps, heading caps, or sentence caps*. Full caps capitalize every character of every word. These are used only in major headings. Headline or heading caps capitalize the first character of each word, subject to exceptions listed below.

Heading caps capitalize “the first and last words and all nouns, pronouns, adjectives, and subordinating conjunctions” (CMS 1993, 282). Also, capitalize the first character after a colon in a title or heading. Otherwise, do not capitalize:

- Articles: *a, an, the*.
- Prepositions, including *against, between, in, of*.
- Conjunctions: *and, but, for, nor, or, so, yet*.
- Infinitive: *to*.

Sentence caps capitalize the first word of a title or heading, the first word after a colon, and proper nouns.

Books and Articles. Titles of books and the names of journals always use heading caps in the text; titles of articles and documents generally do so too and are placed in quotes.

Foreign titles. “The University of Chicago Press recommends following a simple rule: In any language but English, capitalize only the words that would be capitalized in normal prose. For all the languages in question [all major European languages], this means capitalizing the first word of the title and the subtitle and all proper nouns [sentence caps]” (CMS, 1993, 320).

Ethnic/Racial Groups. Generally, the names of ethnic or racial groups are capitalized if they represent a geographical region or language group — for example, Hispanic, Asian, African American, Appalachian. The *Chicago Manual of Style* has additional examples (1993, 246-47).

1. *Generic terms.* “Designations based only on color, size, habitat, customs, or local usage are often lower cased” (CMS 1993, 247).

2. *White & Black.* It is appropriate to capitalize *White* and *Black* when referring to the American racial groups. “The term Black is now often capitalized as the widely accepted name of the dark-skinned group or groups of people originating in Africa” (CMS 1993, 247). As always, be consistent. Other color terms may have disparaging connotations: red, yellow, brown. Do not use these terms.

3. *Compound ethnics.* Do not hyphenate compound nationalities and ethnic or regional terms: *African American, Anglo-German, Middle Eastern*.

Geographical Names. Capitalize place names when these terms are accepted as proper nouns. It should be capitalized as a proper noun when a name applies to a well-recognized specific place.

1. *Geographical terms.* Lowercase “terms for *abstract geographical measures*, such as the equator, equatorial Africa, prime meridian, tropic of Cancer, west, east, south, north” (CMS 1993, 247).

2. *Regions.* Capitalize *Central America*, but not central Europe or central Asia. Capitalize *North Africa*, *West Africa*, and *East Africa*, but not western, eastern, central, or southern Africa. Capitalize *Midwest*, *West*, *South*, or *Southwest*, but generally write *westerner*, *midwesterner*, a *southerner*.

3. *Compounds.* “When a capitalized geographical term comprising more than one word is used as an adjective before a noun, the term should not be hyphenated, since there is no risk of misreading: Middle Eastern journey, North Atlantic fog, . . . , Gulf of Mexico oil spill” (CMS 1993, 248).

Internet Terminology. Usage in this area is frozen by the CMS publication cycle. Be consistent!

- *e-mail* [*email*]. The hyphenated form is found in the AMA, APA, CMS, and MLA style manuals!
- *Web page* [*Web site*]. “Web” is a proper noun in these terms (AMA, APA, CMS, MLA agree).
- *webmaster*, *web*. . . Most other Web terms are spelled lowercased and closed (without a hyphen): *webcam*, *webcast*, *webhead*, *webmail*, *webzine*, etc. Some terms may be spelled open, and *Web* capitalized in formal writing—*Web cam*, *Web cast*, *Web mail*, *Web TV*.

Compound Words

Compound words are two or more words that work together in a specified order. This order cannot be reversed or rearranged without destroying the compound word’s meaning. A dictionary is the best guide to spelling and usage. It is not likely a hyphenated compound if it is not in the dictionary.

Full-time compound words are hyphenated whatever their role in a sentence—as an adjective or a noun. “The court-martial hearing is set for 1000 hours. The hearing will determine whether a court-martial is warranted.” *Court-martial* is a full-time compound word (as is “full-time”). Consult a dictionary.

Conditional compounds are hyphenated as **adjectives** but not when used as nouns.

1. *Adjectival compound.* “The counselor suggested a *role-playing* technique to reduce the stress of encounters, but cautioned that *role playing* alone would not solve the problem.” *Role playing* is a compound adjective, but not a compound noun.

2. *Add a hyphen* to any prefix attached to a proper noun, capitalized abbreviation, or number. For example, in the *post-Freudian* era, the *pre-1960s* civil rights movement, the *pro-HMO* lobby.

3. *Fractions.* “When . . . a fraction is considered a single quantity, it is hyphenated [whether it is used as a noun or as an adjective]. (CMS 2003, 383). *One-fourth*, the audience was comprised of former refugees. A *two-thirds* majority was required to pass the initiative.

4. *Made-up compound.* A compound may be of the *made-up-for-the-occasion* variety: “The *up-to-date* figures were unadjusted.” However, when these terms are used in the predicate, they are not hyphenated: The compound word was *made up for the occasion*. “The unadjusted figures were *up to date*.”

5. *Serial compounds.* When two or more compound modifiers have a common base, this base is sometimes omitted in all but the last modifier, but the hyphens are retained—long- and short-term memory, 2-, 3-, and 10-min trials.

6. Do not hyphenate a compound term using an adverb ending in *-ly*. “The *widely used* term was not yet in the dictionary. Such *clearly understood* terms are eventually documented if they endure.”

 Avoid confusion! A *re-creation* is not the same as *recreation*. A *fast* sailing ship is one designed for speed. A *fast-sailing* ship is one that made a fast passage (CMS 1993, 203).

Prefixes. Most common prefixes do not require a hyphen: *aftereffect*, *antifreeze*, *cofounder*, *Internet*, *microwave*, *oversight*, *preempt*, *reexamine*, *supermarket*, *unbiased*, *underground*. There are many exceptions. When in doubt, check a dictionary. Note the following exceptions:

1. *Same two letters.* If the prefix puts the same two letters together, a hyphen is sometimes inserted. For example, write *anti-industrial*, *co-op*, *non-native*, *post-trial*. But also write: *cooperative*, *coordinate*, *nonnegotiable*, *overrate*, *overreach*, *overrule*, *reelect*, *unnamed*.

2. *Superlatives-diminutives.* Some prefixes, *best-*, *better-*, *ill-*, *lesser-*, *little-*, *well-*, are hyphenated when they precede the noun they modify but are not hyphenated when preceded by a modifier or when used as a predicate adjective. The *ill-advised* attack failed; the strategy was *ill-advised*.

3. *Weird terms.* If the prefix creates an unfamiliar or weird term, a hyphen may improve clarity, for example, *pro-ally*, *anti-college* instead of *proally*, *anticollege*.

The following prefixes *always* require a hyphen:

Prefix	Example	Prefix	Example	Prefix	Example
all-	all-powerful leader	great-	great-grandfather	self-	self-reliant person
ever-	ever-faithful friend	half-	half-baked plan	still-	still-active volcano
ex-	ex-president	much-	much-loved pastor		

Italics & Quotation Marks

Italics and quotation marks are used in the text to highlight words, note and translate words in a language foreign to a reader, indicate irony (scare quotes), or mark words and letters that are referred to as words, not to the meaning they convey.

 Special formatting is appropriate only the first time it is applied to a word a phrase. Thereafter, the word or phrase is presented in plain text unless clarity demands the continued use of italics.

Italics. “Good writers use italics for emphasis only as an occasional adjunct to efficient sentence structure. Overused, italics quickly lose their force. Seldom should as much as a sentence be italicized for emphasis, and never a whole passage” (CMS 2003, 290). *Add italics to a word or phrase only the first time it is used, thereafter use plain text.*

1. **Keywords.** Emphasize a keyword or phrase in your text by placing it in italics. The next time the term or phrase is used, it should be in plain text.

2. **Titles.** The titles of books and the names of periodicals in your text and references.

3. **Words as words.** Words and letters that are referred to as words or letters are set in italics. For example, “the term *American Indian* is inclusive of over 500 ethnic communities.”

4. **Foreign terms.** Non-English words or terms used in your text are set in italics. For example, “*Ya-te-hay* is a form of greeting in the Diné (Navajo) language.” This practice excludes those words that have become incorporated in the English language, such as *laissez-faire* or *arroyo*.

Quotation marks. Use quotation marks other than for quotes only in the following circumstances:

- “Place quotation marks around a word or phrase given in a special sense or purposefully misused” (Gibaldi 91). For example, The Population Council criticized the “outrageous” position of the Church on birth control. Chicago calls these “scare quotes.”

- Use quotation marks to enclose a translation of a non-English term in your text. *Addis Ababa*, the name of the capital of Ethiopia, is literally translated as “new flower.”

Within quotations. Emphasis may be added to a word or phrase in a quotation by placing it in italics. When this is done, the note [emphasis added] or [italics added] must be inserted in brackets at the end of the quotation (within the quotation marks), or if the emphasis comes at the end of the sentence, in parentheses outside the quotation marks.

Numbers

“Among the factors governing the choice between spelling out numbers and using numerals are whether the number is large or small, whether it is an approximation or an exact quantity, what kind of entity it stands for, and what context it appears in” (CMS 2003, 380). Precise measurements are always presented as numerals.

In nontechnical contexts, the following are spelled out: whole numbers from one through one hundred, round numbers, and any number beginning a sentence. For other numbers, numerals are used” (CMS 2003, 380).

1. **Round numbers.** By virtue of their rounding, these numbers are imprecise. They are written out. For example, write “The federal deficit was increased by two hundred billion dollars,” or “San Francisco is about twelve hundred miles from Denver.” But also write, “The race followed a straight course from Denver to San Francisco, a distance of 1,255.6 miles.”

2. *Beginning a sentence.* When numbers or a date are required to open a sentence, write them out. For example: “One hundred five girls and sixteen boys tried out for the varsity soccer team.” If you can, rewrite the sentence so it does not begin with a number.

3. *Mixed numbers?* Do not mix numerals with written numbers when they refer to similar things. For example, write “Only 10 of the 150 tourists were willing to visit the city after the riot.” Do not write, “Only ten of the 150 tourists . . .”

4. *Mixed sets of numbers.* Sometimes two sets of numbers are embedded in a single sentence. For clarity, present one set written out, the other as numerals. For example, write, “There were eighty-three contestants who dropped out before covering 50 miles, and one hundred thirty-five before covering 250 miles.”

5. *Numbers & units.* Generally, do not mix numbers spelled out with symbols; write out the term for the symbols as well. For example, write: the temperature was 45° or *forty-five degrees*; \$20 or *twenty dollars*. Chicago style makes an exception for percentages: it is OK to write *45 percent*.

6. *Compound numbers.* Hyphenate compound numbers from twenty-one to ninety-nine, compounds with a number as the first element, and the written form of fractions.

7. *Ordinal numbers.* Follow the general rules for other numbers. For example, write: “The window for applications was the third to the twenty-third of August.” However, use numerals with ordinal numbers above one hundred. For example, write: “Haile Sellassie I was the 225th Emperor of Ethiopia.”

8. *Centuries.* Write out references to centuries, the eighteenth century, the twenty-first century, in lower cased letters.

 Revolution! New date format. Chicago now recommends using the standard American format--Month Day, Year (e.g., April 1, 2004)--for all full dates, both in the text and in the end/footnotes, references, and bibliographies (see CMS 2003, sec. 6.46). Prior to this edition, dates in references and notes were to be in universal or European format, Day Month Year (e.g., 21 August 2001). This rule has been superseded.

Quotations

Quotations must be placed in quotation marks or indented as a blockquote. All quotations must include a citation, a note, or parenthetical citation, referring the reader to the source document. As a matter of form, quotations should flow with your text and maybe be edited to do so.

 “It is impossible to overemphasize the importance of meticulous accuracy in quoting from the works of others” (CMS 2003, 445). Some changes are permitted:

1. *Added words.* Brackets are required to indicate material or emphasis added to a quote. For example: “They [the Irish Republican Army] initiated a cease fire.”

2. *Added emphasis.* Italics may be used to add emphasis to words or phrases within a quotation or to the entire quotation. This is indicated by (1) adding a note immediately after the change in brackets or (2) by appending a note to the end of the quote in parentheses. For example, write: “He *claimed* [emphasis added] he was innocent” or write: “He *claimed* he was innocent” (emphasis added).

3. *Foreign language.* “If you quote material in a foreign [*sic*] language, you must reproduce all accents and other marks exactly as they appear in the original (école, pietà, tête, leçon, Fähre, año)” (Gibaldi 2003, 80).

4. *Citation in the original.* If you quote material that contains a citation to another work, Chicago style now allows you to ignore the citation.

Correct Errors. For an unusual word choice, concept, term, or spelling, it may be appropriate to emphasize the original is being quoted faithfully. This is done by inserting the Latin term *sic* (thus), in italics or underlined, and in brackets within the quotation (but in parentheses at the end of a quote), immediately following the term.

For example, write: “The ship struck an iceberg and floundered [*sic*], with the loss of all on board.” Or write: “The ship struck an iceberg and floundered” (*sic*). Note, to *flounder* is to thrash about wildly. To *founder* is to fill with water and sink.

 “A verbally accurate quotation that contains minor factual or grammatical errors . . . does a disservice to readers and embarrasses the publisher. [Writers] who notice an error in a passage they wish to quote should paraphrase the original, eliminating the error” (CMS 2003, 445).

Block Quotations. Longer quotations are formatted as block quotes. Blockquotes are continuously indented from the left margin the same distance as a paragraph indent. They are required with longer quotations, although what constitutes “longer” varies widely.

- The Chicago manual advises that quotes of “a hundred words or more--or at least eight lines--are set off as a block quotation” (CMS 2003, 447).
- The Turabian manual advises that “in general a prose quotation of two or more sentences that runs to eight or more lines of text in a paper should be set off from the text in single-spacing and indented in its entirety . . . from the left margin” (1996, 74-75).
- The *MLA Handbook* advises using block quotes when the quotation runs to “more than four lines in your paper” (Gibaldi 1999, 81).
- The *APA Publication Manual* instructs writers to “display a quotation of more than 40 words in a free-standing block of typewritten lines and omit the quotation marks” (1994, 95).

 The Chicago manual also advises that “where quotations are being compared or otherwise used as entities in themselves, it may be better to set them all as block quotations, however short” (2003, 447).

Permitted Changes to Quotations. “Although in a direct quotation the wording, spelling, capitalization, and internal punctuation of the original should be reproduced exactly, the following changes are generally permissible . . . ” (CMS 2003, 447):

1. *Quotation marks.* Double quotes can be changed to single quotes, and vice versa, for merging the quote with the rest of the text.
2. *Initial capital.* If a capital letter begins a quote in the original, that letter should be changed to lowercase when run-in to your text, and vices versa (capitalize the first letter if the quote begins a sentence in your text but is lowercased in the original). If it is essential to alert the reader to this change (e.g., to help them find the original quote), place the altered letter in brackets.
3. *Punctuation.* The final period in a quote may be changed to a comma (and vice versa) to merge with your text.
4. *References in quotes.* Chicago style allows reference citations in a quote to be omitted. And, in Chicago style, notes or references may be inserted into a quote. Most research styles do not allow this.
5. *Typographic errors.* Obvious typographical errors should be corrected, although archaic spellings in older works should generally be preserved unless it is made clear to the reader that the spelling has been updated.
6. *Emphasis in original.* If there are italics or bold font already in the original text for emphasis, then a note should be added to let the reader know *the quote is faithful* [emphasis in original] to the original.

Editing Quotations. Three *ellipsis points* (periods with a single space before, between, and after each period) indicate material has been omitted within a sentence or at the end of a sentence. “The three-dot method is appropriate for most general works and many scholarly ones. . . Where necessary for fidelity to the original and ease of reading, these three may be preceded or followed--depending on where the omission occurs--by a comma, a semicolon, a question mark, or an exclamation point” (CMS 2003, 459).

For example, if the original text reads: “Man’s capacities have never been measured; nor are we to judge of what he can do by any precedents, so little has been tried” (Thoreau 1979, 11), it may be edited to read:

1. *Original punctuation deleted.* If any, the punctuation in the original is retained in the quote. “Man’s capacities have never been measured; . . . so little has been tried” (Thoreau 1979, 11).
2. *Original punctuation retained.* “If other punctuation occurs immediately before a word that is preceded by ellipsis points, that punctuation mark is placed before the word, with the usual intervening space” (Turabian 1996, 80). “Man’s capacities have never been measured; nor are we to judge of what he can do . . . , so little has been tried” (Thoreau 1979, 11). The phrase “by any precedents” has been omitted, but the comma after the phrase is retained.
3. *End of a sentence deleted.* When the quoted material ends in a complete sentence as edited, it is unnecessary to add ellipsis points even if the sentence continues in the original. “Man’s capacities have never been measured; nor are we to judge of what he can do by any precedents” (Thoreau 1993, 11).

Ellipsis not required. “Ellipsis points are normally *not* used (1) before the first word of a quotation, even if the beginning of the original sentence has been omitted; or (2) after the last word of a quotation, even if the end of the original sentence has been omitted, unless the sentence as quoted [in the original] is deliberately incomplete” (CMS 2003, 459).

Chicago Page Formats

The *Chicago Manual of Style* is focused on book publishing, so it has few instructions to offer for formatting papers. Turabian’s *Manual for Writers* is the official guide to applying Chicago style to “term papers, theses, and dissertations,” that is, final manuscripts.

1. *Margins.* “The normal page dimensions are 8½ by 11 inches. Leave a margin of at least one inch on all four edges of the page. Some institutions require more, particularly on the left, where binding reduces the margin” (Turabian 1996, 252).

2. *Fonts.* “The eminently readable Times Roman is perhaps the best choice. . . . Twelve-point type (ten characters per inch) for text and ten-point (twelve characters per inch) for notes will meet the requirements of most institutions” (Turabian 1996, 247-8).

3. *Indents.* The standard indent is one-half inch. This applies to all indents: paragraphs, hanging indents in references, and block quotes.

4. *Paper.* Use only 8½ by 11-inch white paper. A 20 pound or 24 pounds, high brightness (80+), paper works best. Avoid or photocopy lighter papers (16 pounds or less) and textured papers such as an erasable bond.

5. *Justification.* “Right margins should be justified (aligned) only if it can be done without leaving large gaps between words. When lines are automatically justified by a computer, all hyphenation must be carefully checked and adjusted” (Turabian 1996, 252). While aligning text to the right margin makes for a neat page, it can be more difficult to read. Manuscripts submitted for publication use a ragged right margin for these reasons.

6. *Spacing.* “The text should be double-spaced except for block quotations, notes [and references], captions, and long headings [that wrap to two lines], which should be single spaced with a blank space between items” (Turabian 1996, 253). The latter is sometimes called *block paragraph* spacing.

7. *Page numbers* for each page beginning a major section of a paper (the first text page, bibliography, notes, appendix) are placed at the bottom center of the page three-quarters of an inch from the page edge. Page numbers on other pages go in the upper right corner, double spaced above the text.

GREAT WESTERN UNIVERSITY

**ELEMENTS OF CHICAGO STYLE:
CENTER TITLE IN FULL CAPS**

Abstract. An abstract is not too common in short papers. But many research journals require an abstract with papers they review and publish, and a dissertation or thesis will require an abstract as well. It adds a nice professional touch to good term papers. Write a brief summary of the topic you have investigated, touching on the method of study, and closing with a summary of what you learned. Abstracts range from 150 to 500 words depending on the scale of the work. Short papers need short abstracts.

BY

ABAGAIL ANN AUTHOR

Department of Alchemy

Medieval Magic 101

April 1, 2005

The page number is not shown on the first page. It is numbered with a lowercase letter, so the first text page is page 1.

**ELEMENTS OF CHICAGO STYLE:
CENTER TITLE IN FULL CAPS**

Introduction: First Level Heading

The first text page is page one. The title page is nominally numbered with a lowercase roman numeral that is not shown. The page number is centered, 3/4 inch from the bottom of the first text page, and the first note and reference pages. Number other pages top right. Page headers are not used in Turabian style.

Second Level Heading

Block format is required with longer quotes, usually more than four lines, although the *CMS* has not set a specific standard. Single-space within block quotes, double-space before and after.

This is a delicious evening when the whole body is one sense and imbibes delight through every pore. I go and come with a strange liberty in Nature, a part of herself. As I walk along the stony shore of the pond in my shirt-sleeves . . . all the elements are unusually congenial to me.¹

Third-level heading. This *run-in* or *paragraph* the heading is indented, set in a bold font and heading caps.

1. Henry David Thoreau, *Walden* (New York: New American Library), 90. Footnotes are single-spaced within the margins.

Footnotes

Footnotes must be placed, or at least must begin, on the page where they are referred to [indicated by a superscript numeral in the text]. A short rule or separator separates the text and footnotes. If a footnote runs over to the following page, a separator should be inserted on that page. Each footnote must begin on a new line, indented the same amount as paragraphs in the text. Footnotes are usually single-spaced, with a blank line between notes.

Either of the two styles may be followed in numbering footnotes. The simpler one is to use numerals on the line followed by a period, as in the first example. The older style uses superscript numerals like footnote numbers in the text, without punctuation. Be consistent!

Footnotes can create a bewildering maze for the reader to unravel. As a consequence, “the use of *op. cit.* and *loc. cit.*, formerly common in scholarly references, is now discouraged” (Turabian 1996, 138). Although *ibid.* and *idem* are still used; they are also sources of confusion for the interested reader. Instead, after the first full reference, use a shortened reference in subsequent citations.

23. Turabian, *Manual for Writers*, 139.

 Clarity is required in research writing. Never confuse your reader. Add the bibliography to the paper when using footnotes. This allows the reader to find a source readily.

Headings & Lists

Headings. Three levels of subheadings are shown in the graphic. The main headings--the title, the heading for the endnotes, bibliography, or appendix--are presented in full caps, centered, in a bold font, dropped *two inches* from the top of the page (one inch below the margin). Subheadings are presented in a bold font, lower levels are in italics as well.

Lists (Seriation, Enumeration). Chicago uses the term “lists” to refer to *enumeration* or *seriation*. Seriation is the process of (1) listing a series of topics, (2) marked by numbers or letters in parentheses,

(3) to delineate subjects that merit individual attention in the text. This paragraph gives an example of a *run-in list* in Chicago terminology or *sentence seriation* in a more traditional vocabulary.

Paragraph seriation. If each element in the series requires a separate paragraph or is a complete sentence, these are set flush with the left margin, with longer sentences aligned as text blocks to the right of the number. An introductory clause or sentence ending with a colon typically introduces the series:

1. This form of seriation or *vertical list* is useful in detailing and summarizing an argument or perhaps the results of a research study. "If items run over a line, the second and subsequent lines are usually indented [hanging indent]. . . . aligned with the first word following the numeral" (CMS 2003, 272).

2. "All items in a list should be syntactically alike--that is, all should be noun forms, phrases, full sentences, or whatever the context requires" (CMS 2003, 271).

1. *Lower level run-in heading?* The paragraph list format merges into that for the lowest-level heading. The two can readily be combined when a fourth-level heading is needed.

 "Bullets (heavy dots □ . . .) make good visual signposts in unnumbered lists but can lose their force if used too frequently" (CMS 2003, 272).

Place the page number bottom center on pages beginning a major section.																					
<p style="text-align: center;">BIBLIOGRAHY</p> <p>Arendt, Hannah. <i>The Human Condition</i>. 1958. Reprint, Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1998.</p> <p>Dumper, Michael. "Israeli Settlement in the Old City of Jerusalem." <i>Journal of Palestine Studies</i> 21, no. 4 (1992): 32-53.</p> <p>Friedman, Howard S., ed. <i>Personality and Disease</i>. New York: Wiley, 1990.</p> <p>Hemingway, Ernest. "The Big Two-Hearted River." In <i>The Nick Adams Stories</i>, ed. Philip Young, 159-180. New York: Bantam Books, 1973.</p> <p>Kelly, John D., and Martha Kaplan. "Ritual Studies." <i>Annual Review of Research in Anthropology</i> 19 (1990): 119-50.</p> <p>Kuhn, Thomas S. <i>The Structure of Scientific Revolutions</i>, 2nd ed. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1970.</p> <p>"Taking the Business Cycle's Pulse." <i>The Economist</i>, October 28, 1995, 89-90.</p> <p>Whitman, Walt. <i>Complete Poetry and Selected Prose</i>. Edited by James E. Miller Jr. 1855. Reprint, Boston: Houghton Mifflin Company, 1959.</p> <p>Wilson, Edward O. "Back from Chaos." <i>Atlantic Monthly</i>, March 1998, 41-62.</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">8</p> <p>Place tables and figures in your text close to where they are first discussed. In manuscripts for publication, they come at the end of the paper on separate pages. Tables and figures are numbered consecutively. Tables begin with a label; figures are followed by a <i>legend</i>.</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Table 1 <i>Homicides by Race of Victim: the United States 1993</i></p> <table border="1" data-bbox="873 957 1317 1121"> <thead> <tr> <th>Race</th> <th>Population^a</th> <th>Homicides</th> <th>Rate^b</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Black</td> <td>29,986</td> <td>12,114</td> <td>40.5*</td> </tr> <tr> <td>White</td> <td>199,686</td> <td>12,153</td> <td>6.1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Other</td> <td>19,038</td> <td>635</td> <td>3.3**</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Total</td> <td>248,710</td> <td>24,932</td> <td>10.0</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p><i>Source:</i> Bureau of the Census, <i>Statistical Abstract of the United States: 1993</i> (Washington, DC: U.S. Government Printing Office, 1993).</p> <p>^aPopulation in 1000s. ^bRate per 100,000 persons. *$p < .05$, two-tailed test. **$p < .01$, two-tailed test.</p> <p>There are three kinds of notes that may be added to a table: (1) general notes giving the source, (2) specific notes or table footnotes noted with superscript letters, and (3) probability level notes. The <i>Chicago Manual of Style</i> refers you to the <i>Publication Manual of the American Psychological Association</i>, 5th edition, for detailed instructions on formatting tables.</p>	Race	Population ^a	Homicides	Rate ^b	Black	29,986	12,114	40.5*	White	199,686	12,153	6.1	Other	19,038	635	3.3**	Total	248,710	24,932	10.0
Race	Population ^a	Homicides	Rate ^b																		
Black	29,986	12,114	40.5*																		
White	199,686	12,153	6.1																		
Other	19,038	635	3.3**																		
Total	248,710	24,932	10.0																		
10																					

Tables

"A table offers an excellent means of presenting a large number of individual, similar facts so that they are easy to scan and compare. A simple table can give information that would require several paragraphs to present textually, and it can do so more clearly. . . . For excellent advice on table preparation, consult the *Publication Manual of the American Psychological Association*" (CMS 2003, 496).

- Number tables consecutively as they appear in your text. Center tables close in the text where they are first mentioned. If possible, insert the table at the end of a paragraph. Do not split tables across two pages. If there is not enough room at the bottom of a page, continue your text and place the table at the top of the next page.

- Each table must have a label beginning with the table number and describing the contents. The label needs to inform the reader what the table presents (coefficients, means, percentages, rates, etc.), the time frame, and the coverage (e.g., United States, Illinois, Cook County, Chicago, South Side).
- Use block paragraph spacing for tables, single spacing within the label (heading), the table, and the notes; double spacing between these blocks.
- Each row and column must have a heading. Subheadings may be used to expand or clarify headings. Chicago style tables may use symbols in column headings, e.g., % or \$.
- If the contents of a table are drawn or adapted from a published source, note that as the first footnote to the table. Notes that apply to the table as a whole are not numbered or lettered.
- Add footnotes notes to explain the table contents. These are labeled “a, b, c, etc.”
- The last note at the bottom of the table is reserved for reporting levels of probability. Tradition dictates the use of asterisks to annotate statistics in the table, for example: $*p < .05$, $**p < .01$, $***p < .001$.

 The more information is put on a table, the harder it is to read. Readers rarely study tables. “An informative table supplements—it does not duplicate—the text” (APA 1994, 84).

Chicago Endnotes & Footnotes

Chicago Notes are arranged in the order cited. Notes are commonly single-spaced. To indicate a citation in your text, place a superscript number after punctuation, preferably one citation only per sentence at the end of a sentence. Multiple references may be combined in the endnote or footnote. Do not note or cite headings, subheadings, or titles.

1. *Authors.* Give authors’ and editors’ full names in normal order. If there is no author, use the title. List up to *three* co-authors to work; four or more, the first followed by *et al.* or *and others* (CMS 2003, secs. 17.28-17.30). Bibliographies list up to ten authors, then add *et al.*
2. *Multiple works* by the same author in different notes list the full reference. With a subsequent citation to the same source, give the lead author a short title and page.
3. *Titles.* All titles require heading capitalization. Titles of journal papers, chapters in edited volumes or anthologies, reports, and newspaper articles are placed within quotes.
4. *Date.* Chicago style now prefers full dates American style, in month day, year format.
5. *Indent notes like a paragraph or with a full indent like this list.*
6. *Electronic sources* are referenced like their print counterparts, with an added URL. Electronic sources on media other than the Internet require a note to that effect. The optional access date is placed in parentheses after the URL. See the example in the list below.

Authors - Books - Compilations

One to Three Authors - Reprint

1. Hannah Arendt, *The Human Condition* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1958; reprint, Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1998), 123.
2. Pierre Bourdieu and Jean-Claude Passeron, *Reproduction in Education, Society, and Culture* (London: Sage, 1977), 123.

Diana Hacker, *Research and Documentation in the Electronic Age* (Boston: Bedford Books, 1997).
<http://www.bedfordbooks.com/> (October 8, 1998).

Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, and Joseph M. Williams, *The Craft of Research* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1995), 123.

Four to Ten Authors

Howard Schuman and others, *Racial Attitudes in America: Trends and Interpretations*, rev. ed. (Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 1997).

Corporate Author

Congressional Budget Office, *Changes in Living Arrangements of the Elderly: 1960-2030* (Washington, DC: U.S. Government Printing Office, 1988).

Editor as Author

Howard S. Friedman, ed., *Personality, and Disease* (New York: Wiley, 1990).

Anthology - Compilation - Edited Book

Walt Whitman, *Complete Poetry and Selected Prose*, ed. James E. Miller, Jr. (Boston: Houghton Mifflin Company, 1959).

Ernest Hemingway, "The Big Two-Hearted River," in *The Nick Adams Stories*, ed. Philip Young (New York: Bantam Books, 1973), 159-180.

Edition Other Than the First

Thomas S. Kuhn, *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions*, 2nd ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1970).

Translation

Nikos Kazantzakis, *Zorba the Greek*, trans. Carl Wildman (New York: Simon & Schuster, 1952).

Journals & Newspapers*Annual Review*

John D. Kelly and Martha Kaplan, "Ritual Studies," *Annual Review of Research in Anthropology* 19 (1990): 119-50.

Journal Article (Paged by Volume)

Michael Dietler, "'Our Ancestors the Gauls': Archaeology, Ethnic Nationalism, and the Manipulation of Celtic Identity in Modern Europe," *American Anthropologist* 96 (1994): 584-605.

Mark Wheelis, "Biological Warfare at the 1346 Siege of Caffa," *Emerging Infectious Diseases* 8, no. 9 (September 2002): 971-975, <http://www.cdc.gov/ncidod/eid/vol8no9/> (December 9, 2003).

Journal Paged by Issue

Michael Dumper, "Israeli Settlement in the Old City of Jerusalem," *Journal of Palestine Studies* 21, no. 4 (1992): 32-53.

Magazine Articles (No Author)

Edward O. Wilson, "Back from Chaos," *Atlantic Monthly*, March 1998, 41-62.

"Taking the Business Cycle's Pulse," *The Economist*, October 28, 1995, 89-90.

Newspaper Articles (Book Review, No Author, Online)

Patricia Nelson Limerick, "Dancing with Professors: The Trouble with Academic Prose," *New York Times Book Review*, October 31, 1993, 3, 23-24.

Leslie Camhi, "Art of the City," review of *New York Modern: The Arts and the City*, by William B. Scott, and Peter M. Rutkoff, *Village Voice*, June 15, 1999, 154.

"Feds Close Vail Logging Road," *Colorado Daily* [Boulder], July 27-29, 1999, 2.

John Markoff, "Voluntary Rules Proposed to Help Insure Privacy for Internet Users," *New York Times*, June 5, 1996. <http://www.nytimes.com/.../yo5dat.html> (June 10, 1996).

Reports and Papers*Conference Papers*

S-Y. Kuroda, "Whether We Agree or Not: A Comparative Syntax of English and Japanese," in *Papers from the Second International Workshop on Japanese Syntax*, ed. William J. Poser (Stanford, CA: CSLI, 1988), 103-43.

Maggie McFadden, "Weaving the Cloth of International Sisterhood" (paper presented at the National Women's Studies Association conference, Minneapolis, June 1988), 123.

PhD Dissertation

Stephen A. McNeary, "Where Fire Came Down: Social and Economic Life of the Niska" (Ph.D. dissertation, Bryn Mawr College, 1976).

Research Report

Elizabeth Morrissey, "Work and Poverty in Metro and Nonmetro Areas," Rural Development Research Report No. 81 (Washington, DC: U.S. Department of Agriculture, 1991).

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"Documenting Sources from the World Wide Web" (Modern Language Association, February 3, 2000). <http://www.mla.org/style/sources.htm> (February 17, 2000).

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Duane F. Alwin, "Equity Theory," in *Encyclopedia of Sociology*, ed. Edgar F. Borgatta and Marie L. Borgatta (New York: Macmillan, 1992), 563-575.

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Peter G. Bergman, "Relativity," in *Encyclopedia Britannica*, 15th ed., vol. 26 (Chicago: Encyclopedia Britannica, 1998), 501-508.

"Genetic Engineering," in *Compton's Interactive Encyclopedia*, ver. 2.0 (Carlsbad, CA: Compton's NewMedia, Inc., 1994). CD-ROM.

"Stock Market Crash in 1929," in *Britannica On-line*. 1995. <http://www.eb.com/> (July 1, 1998). *Computer Program*

Luc Anselin, *SPACESTAT: A Program for the Statistical Analysis of Spatial Data*. Computer program (Santa Barbara, CA: National Center for Geographic Information and Analysis, University of California, 1993).

Statistical Abstract

Bureau of the Census, "Higher Education Price Indexes: 1965-1991," in *Statistical Abstract of the United States: 1993*, 113th ed. (Washington, DC: US GPO, 1993), Table 277.

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Bourdieu, Pierre. "The Market of Symbolic Goods." In *The Field of Cultural Production: Essays in Art and Literature*, ed. Randal Johnson, 112-141. New York: Columbia University Press, 1993.

Friedman, Howard S., ed. *Personality and Disease*. New York: Wiley, 1990.

Hemingway, Ernest. "The Big Two-Hearted River." In *The Nick Adams Stories*, edited by Philip Young, 159-180. New York: Bantam Books, 1973.

Whitman, Walt. *Complete Poetry and Selected Prose*. Edited by James E. Miller Jr. 1855. Reprint, Boston: Houghton Mifflin Company, 1959.

Books

Arendt, Hannah. *The Human Condition*. 1958. Reprint, Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1998.

Booth, Wayne C., Gregory G. Colomb, and Joseph M. Williams. *The Craft of Research*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1995.

Congressional Budget Office. *Changes in the Living Arrangements of the Elderly: 1960-2030*. Washington, DC: U.S. Government Printing Office, 1988.

French, R. M., trans. *The Way of a Pilgrim and The Pilgrim Continues His Way*. New York: Ballantine Books-Random House, 1974.

Kuhn, Thomas S. *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions*, 2nd ed. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1970.

Schuman, Howard, Charlotte Steeh, Lawrence Bobo, and Maria Krysan. *Racial Attitudes in America: Trends and Interpretations*, rev. ed. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 1997.

Journals & Newspapers

Camhi, Leslie. "Art of the City." Review of *New York Modern: The Arts and the City*, by William B. Scott, and Peter M. Rutkoff. *Village Voice*, June 15, 1999, 154.

Dietler, Michael. "'Our Ancestors the Gauls': Archaeology, Ethnic Nationalism, and the Manipulation of Celtic Identity in Modern Europe." *American Anthropologist* 96 (1994): 584-605.

Kelly, John D., and Martha Kaplan. "Ritual Studies." *Annual Review of Research in Anthropology* 19 (1990): 119-50.

Markoff, John. "Voluntary Rules Proposed to Help Insure Privacy for Internet Users." *New York Times*, June 5, 1996. <http://www.nytimes.com/.../yo5dat.html> (June 10, 1996).

"Taking the Business Cycle's Pulse." *The Economist*, October 28, 1995, 89-90.

Wheelis, Mark. "Biological Warfare at the 1346 Siege of Caffa." *Emerging Infectious Diseases* 8, no. 9 (September 2002): 971-975. <http://www.cdc.gov/ncidod/eid/vol8no9/> (December 9, 2003).

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American Heritage Dictionary of the English Language, 3rd ed. Boston, MA: Houghton Mifflin, 1992.

Bergman, Peter G. "Relativity." In *Encyclopedia Britannica*, 15th ed., Vol. 26, 501-508. Chicago: Encyclopedia Britannica, 1998.

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McNeary, Stephen A. "Where Fire Came Down: Social and Economic Life of the Niska." Ph.D. dissertation, Bryn Mawr College, 1976.

Morrissey, Elizabeth. "Work and Poverty in Metro and Nonmetro Areas." Rural Development Research Report No. 81. Washington, DC: U.S. Department of Agriculture, 1991.

All health and success does me good, however far off and withdrawn it may appear; all disease and failure helps to make me sad and does me evil, however much sympathy it may have with me or I with it. --Thoreau

7) CHAPTER SEVEN: LATIN ABBREVIATIONS AND EXPRESSIONS

Understand common Latin abbreviations used in writing

Understand the meaning of Latin abbreviations used in writing

Understand the meaning of common Latin expressions

This chapter provides two tables showing common Latin abbreviations and expressions used by technical communicators.

Common Latin Abbreviations Used in Writing

Latin abbreviations are appropriate in footnotes, bibliographies, and informal writing (**e.g.**, the information in parentheses).

In business, formal, and technical writing, use the English equivalent of the abbreviation to avoid misinterpretation by your readers:

Many communication tools can be used to promote the launch of a new store (**for example**, flyers, press releases, radio announcements, **and so on**).

Note: It is best to create content using "plain language" principles. Plain language (also called plain English) is a writing style that is simple and direct but not simplistic or patronizing. When writing in plain language, use short sentences with simple words. Avoid jargon, acronyms, and abbreviations.

In the first reading, plain language should be visually inviting, logically organized, and understandable.

Abbreviation	Latin	English
A.M.	ante meridiem	before noon
c. or ca	circa	about; approximately
cf.	confer	compare
c.v.	curriculum vitae	curriculum vitae
ead.	eadem	in the same place; author (female form of <i>ibid.</i>)
e.g.	exempli gratia	for example; for instance

Abbreviation	Latin	English
etc.	et cetera	and so on; and other people/things
et al.	et alii (masculine plural) or et aliae (feminine plural) or et alia (neutral plural)	and other people
et seq.	et sequens	and the following pages
fl.	floruit	he/she flourished; used to indicate the high point of a person's life or career when his/her dates of birth are unknown
ib, ibid.	ibidem	in the same place; relates to the immediately prior source. author (male)
i.e.	id est	that is
loc. cit.	loco citato	in the place already mentioned; relates to sources before the immediately prior citation
N.B.	nota bene	note well/carefully
op. cit.	opere citato	in the work already mentioned; relates to sources before the immediately prior citation [loc. cit. and op. cit. are synonymous, with op. cit. probably more frequent]
p.	paper	page
P.M.	post meridiem	after noon
pp.	pluta paper	pages
p.p.	per pro; per procurationem	on behalf of; used when someone signs a letter by authority or proxy because another person is not available
pro tem.	pro tempore	for the time; temporarily

Abbreviation	Latin	English
P.S.	post scriptum	after writing
Q.E.D.	quod erat demonstrandum	which was to be shown
q.v.	quod vide	which see; used to cross-refer to material that can be found elsewhere within the same book or piece of writing. q.v. is not synonymous with cf.; the latter cross-refers to external material
sc. or scil.	scilicet; scire licet	that is to say, namely
sic	sic	thus, or literally
s.v.	sub voce	under the word; used in connection with alphabetically arranged reference works
v.	versus	against
v.	vide, imperative of video	see; look up
v.	voce	voice; word
v.g.	verbi gratia	for example
v. inf.	vide infra	see below
viz	videlicet	that is to say, namely [a keynote abbreviation for academic pedants or post-modernists. There is no full stop (signifying an abbreviation), because the "z" is not a letter but a sign of contraction].
vs.	versus	against
v.v.	vice versa	the other way round

Commonly Used Latin Expressions

Latin Expression	English
a fortiori	with even stronger reason
a posteriori	from effects to causes; reasoning based on past experience
a priori	from causes to effects; conclusions drawn from assumptions; from what comes before; deductive reasoning
ab initio	from the beginning
ad hoc	improvised
ad infinitum	never ending
ad lib	at will; off the top of the head
bis	second (as in V34.bis)
bona fide	in good faith
caveat	a caution/warning (e.g., <i>caveat emptor</i> - "let the buyer beware")
curricula vitae	the courses of one's life; résumés
curriculum vitae	the course of one's life; résumé
de facto	from the fact (rather than by right)
de jure	from the law
ex officio	out of one's duty or office
ex post facto	after the fact, retrospectively

Latin Expression	English
infra	below
in situ	in its original place
in toto	in its entirety
inter alia	among other things
locus classicus	standard or most authoritative source
ipso facto	by the fact itself
non sequitur	it does not follow
passim	here and there; throughout; in several places
per capita	per head
prima facie	at first sight; on the face of it
pro bono	for the public good, at no cost
pro rata	in proportion
quid pro quo	something in return
scilicet; scire licet	that is to say, namely
sic	thus used; thus spelt
sine die	without a day, with no time fixed
sine qua non	without which not, essential precondition

Latin Expression	English
status quo	things as they are
stet	as it was originally
supra	above
vide	see
vide supra	see above
viva (voce)	oral examination

8) CHAPTER EIGHT: SAMPLE CORRECTIONS TO PAPERS

Read a sample response paper

Understand how the instructor provides response

Learn some of the dos and donts of writing a response paper

RESPONSE PAPER

LAST NAME: EFGH

FIRST NAME: ABCD

STUDENT COUNTRY: UGANDA

PROGRAM CODE: DSDD

COURSE CODE: ACA-401D

PERIOD NUMBER: 1

INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA Gulma

Gulma, Kabiru

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Gulma, Kabiru

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Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did not- use Zotero to insert references

The author did did not- use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP samples below):

1. Writing a good academic essay (EUCLID 2021, 1-4)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 5-13)
3. Some rules of thumb for writing papers (EUCLID 2021, 14-16)
4. Style guide (EUCLID 2021, 24-26)
5. American Vs. British English (EUCLID 2021, 27-35)

Gulma, Kabiru

Do not leave space after opening a bracket before the first word!

WRITING A GOOD ACADEMIC ESSAY

1) INTRODUCTION

At firstfirst, I was confused yet too excited about this journey of pursuing a PHD Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.) I did not know where to start from. For the past couple of daysdays, I tried to familiarize myself with EUCLID protocols and all that is expected of me as a studentstudent, but it is surely over whelming at the start with many documents wondering what to start with. I have taken time to breathe in and calm myself. That is how on 9th November, 2021, I managed to register/log in on the LMS portal. I have read through the documents sent to me and watched the tutorials that are the guide to this response paper. Am really nervous but am hoping that I do a good job. I have always assumed my English to be excellent being that it is our official language in UgandaUganda, and it is the language of instruction from pre-primary to this level am at however I have realized that I still have a lot of learning, unlearning, relearning to do.

Gulma, Kabiru

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Nevertheless, I have read the ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack revised by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma, watched the ACA-401D basic tutorial video which was delivered by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck on language, citation styles and how to

Gulma, Kabiru

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use paragraphs/headings when writing response papers, I realized that learning never ends there is a lot of learning, ~~relearning~~~~relearning~~, and unlearning to be done. To have a good essay one has to first of all be abreast with the basics of writing. I have established that the smallest of things like punctuations, spellings are important in essay writing.

~~Also~~~~Also~~, the English version to be used is fundamental in essay writing. I have noted that when writing an ~~essay~~~~essay~~, one should from the onset decide on the English version to be used in the essay otherwise one will be bound to make mistakes.

In this response paper, my discussion will be on five major concepts that I have learned from the ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack for period one and basic tutorial video these will include essay writing, plagiarism, some of the rules of thumb for writing, style guide, American vs. British English language style.

2) WRITING A GOOD ACADEMIC ESSAY

The first chapter of the ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack for period one deliberates on the basics of essay writing. It expounds how to write a good essay stating the preparations needed in essay writing, the tips on essay writing and conclusion.

When one is planning to write a paper, they should adequately plan on how they are going to carry out the task at hand. They should commit time to the task. They should know what they are starting with and ending with. One should have a writing plan as it helps them to be focused and organized in executing task before them.

An academic essay is aimed at answering a question or task. And for it to be effective it should be backed up by evidence and examples. In doing this, one must prepare accordingly by undertaking thorough research about the issues they are writing about (EUCLID 2021, 2). One should have a plan and how to approach the assignment and set aside time to undertake adequate research ~~so as~~ to come up with a good essay. I concur with this argument because many a times the subject being written about is not new and one is not reinventing the wheel but building on previous research hence literature review vital for one to write a good essay. It is important for one to take notes while researching because when drafting their ~~paper~~~~paper~~, the information may be useful. Key to note is that when taking the notes, they should write the sources like the author, publisher, and date of publication so that such information will be used in referencing.

Important to note is that an essay should have structure to follow. One should structure their essay to communicate their ideas and answer the question. For EUCLID, the accepted structure should have an introduction, ~~body~~~~body~~, and conclusion (EUCLID 2021, 3). The structure makes the essay to look organized and communicate in an orderly manner. I believe it also promotes uniformity and helps the lecturers and professors when reviewing the students' work.

When writing an essay, one should understand the requirement of the task at hand. They should understand the task/assignment so that even when they are

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~~researching~~researching, they know what specifically they are researching about otherwise they will end up with a lot of information which may not necessarily be relevant to the subject they are writing about.

I have noted that when writing academic ~~essays~~essays, one should be clear on the English version they are using otherwise a lot of mistakes may arise hence its prudent to choose the version to be used.

The ACA-401D period one (1) course pack and the 14-minute video gave me an insight of what one should be armed with if they are to become good academic writers. Various perspectives in this course have addressed the queries I had in my mind on professional writing. I believe this will help me throughout my journey in this pursuit of doctoral studies and professional work. The video was ~~practical~~practical, and I believe with practice it will become permanent on my side.

3) PLAGIARISM

According to EUCLID (2021, 5) plagiarism is “using a source of information without giving credit to the author of that information.” Merriam Webster defines plagiarism as the act of using another person’s words or ideas without giving credit to that person: the act of plagiarizing something ([Merriam-Webster, Inc. 2021](https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/plagiarism)). (<https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/plagiarism> 11/11/2021 at 9: 39 am). This can be intentional or non-intentional. It is important to ~~acknowledge the source of information at all times~~always acknowledge the source of information failure to adhere has repercussions. I have learnt that plagiarism is wrong and unethical (EUCLID 2021, 5). ~~Personally~~Personally, I believe one who does not acknowledge another’s ~~work~~work, yet they have used are not only disrespectful but incompetent and they should not expect to be accorded any courtesy as authors. I will ~~desist from plagiarism at all times~~always desist from plagiarism. It is always important to give to Ceaser what belongs to Ceaser like Jesus said. ~~Therefore~~Therefore, when one uses information or borrows information from any ~~source~~source, they should acknowledge it. I know plagiarism is a common vice at times some of the good writers have fallen victim to this vice. ~~So~~So, it is good that from the onset at EUCLID we are reminded of the basic principles or ethics in essay writing so that one cannot use the excuse of ignorance though it does not exonerate one.

I have noted that a writer can give credit to the source of their information when using any quote, paraphrase, statistic/data, or visuals (such as a graph) that is borrowed from another source.

~~In order to~~To avoid plagiarism, the solution is to properly CITE the author or source that has provided the information one is using (EUCLID 2021, 6).

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In US English, punctuations are placed before closing the inverted comma except if a citation follows immediately.

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4) SOME RULES OF THUMB FOR WRITING PAPERS

I have noted that when writing an ~~essayessay~~, it is good to personalize the essay, give your line of thought and argument which is evidence based. Even when one ~~critics~~ another's work, one should empathize with others even when with divergent thoughts the writing should be respectful (EUCLID 2021, 14). Writers therefore should not just discredit ones without evidence.

When writing an ~~essayessay~~, one should ensure that the main thesis is stated from the onset as this sets the momentum and flow of the essay. Writers should be focused when writing. They should avoid general statements in their work. I have established that when writing, short sentences are emphasized, long sentences then not only to confuse but at times communicate different information. Writing is not like talking where can talk a lot yet communicating a small thing. For ~~exampleexample~~, I normally have the challenge of writing long sentences ~~due to the fact that~~because I write what exactly am thinking something, I need to first synthesis my information before I communicate it.

I concur that indeed a writer should ensure that their essay is interesting so that the reader is kept motivated to read more of your essay. The writer should make an interesting and catchy introduction.

~~Also~~Also, when writing assertions should be supported with evidence and not left hanging this makes your paper to be credible. As the assertions are supported credit should be given to those sources so that plagiarism is avoided, for plagiarism is unacceptable and should be avoided at all costs.

One ~~has to~~must take time reading, re-reading, and editing their work. Where support is needed one should seek it from others that deems to be helpful like the tutors (EUCLID 2021, 16).

5) STYLE GUIDE

EUCLID (2021, 24) defines a style guide as a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent. I have established that a style guide is essential if the finished publication is to be coherent and consistent hence as a writer this should be taken seriously since for writing the ultimate is publication. A style guide provides a means of documenting basic rules or features of one's writing. A style guide is an invaluable tool in essay writing when writing one apply it accordingly. From the review I have learned that there is no ~~particular~~single authoritative source on style for written English hence there is, and will always be, a certain amount of debate on elements of style.

I have gathered that a writing style guide aids with consistency and improves ones' writing skills (EUCLID 2021, 25). This style guide will indeed guide me in my writing not

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only in my doctoral studies but also in my professional work since I participate a lot in drafting policy documents.

I have learnt that EUCLID has ~~particular~~-recommended styles that is the Chicago Rules (Turabian), though other internationally accepted styles like American English is accepted. ~~Personally~~~~Personally~~, it ~~is~~~~is~~ my first time to learn about the Chicago Rules (Turabian). I have never encountered it and excited to learn and use it. Am optimistic that I will learn and enjoy using it with ease as time goes on.

As for the EUCLID template it is a life saver for me as not only does it guide the student but is easy and simple to follow. It even makes the essay look superb before one ~~actually reads~~. The presentation and layout ~~is~~~~are~~ recommendable. I also like it that one is guided on the number or range of issues to discuss in their response paper otherwise for some who have a lot to write, they can write a response paper of more than 20 pages.

6) AMERICAN VS. BRITISH ENGLISH

My country being a former of the British Colony we as a country are inclined to the British English most of the times, even the desktop and my tablet that I use by default they use the British English but never the less many times when writing or editing policy documents you will find a blend of both the American and the British English because the difference is mostly on the spellings and pronunciations but not on the meanings? ~~So~~~~So~~, we do not mind about the version. EUCLID (2021, 27) states that American and British English ~~are~~ more similar than different, especially with "educated" or "scientific" English. Most divergence can be ascribed to differing national histories and cultural development.

~~However~~~~However~~, with this literature I have established that the two version should not be used interchangeably at EUCLID, one should decide on what version to use from the outset and stick to it throughout the essay. -I will endeavor to follow that guidance.

7) CONCLUSION

This session being my inaugural step for pursuing Ph.D. in Sustainable Development and Diplomacy (DSDD) it has warmed me up and will set the pace for my progress. It is a very enriching experience to read the ACA-401D period one (1) course pack and orientation documents and to watch the videos delivered by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck. I liked it that the video was precise and spot on. I know I will watch it very now and then until I become a master in EUCLID accepted writing style.

This session made me realize that the English still need to learn, ~~unlearn~~~~unlearn~~ and relearn many things ~~so~~~~as~~-to become a good scholar and writer. I guess it is ok to now start from the basics that are normally ignored as obvious. In my culture there is a saying that learning never ends until one ~~dies~~~~dies~~. I have confirmed that, and true learning is never ending.

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Word contraction is informal, always write words in full!

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ACA-401D PERIOD I

PAGE

This course pack ACA-401D period one (1) course pack will be my invaluable tool until I conclude this doctoral program. I also want to state that it might take time to master it all but definitely I will apply it.

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